

1 **A Mathematical Theory of the Universe: The Complex Numbered Theory of**
2 **General Relativity**

3 **D. Hardy B.S Physics**

4 **D.m.hardy@vikes.csuohio.edu**

5 **Abstract:** This paper generalizes the mathematical apparatus of general relativity
6 to include new operators such as the zoom operator and generalized mathematical
7 objects for complex spaces. CGR addresses the nature of space-time at the
8 quantum zoom or quantum scale as quantum space time which give rise to
9 quantum space-time coordinates for the trajectory for the internal motions of a
10 particle by generalized zitterbewegung according to a relativistic version of the
11 debroglie-bohm quantum theory.

12 **§ 1**

13 **A Mathematical Theory of the Universe Requires A Multidimensional**
14 **Mathematical Structure**

15 Q.E.D [1] is well able to give a good description of the wave mechanics
16 [2] of matter, in the sense that from Q.E.D, we have an almost satisfactory
17 mathematical image of the major quantum experiments [3] performed which craft
18 modern QM, and field theories like M-Theory [4] and String Theory [5], and
19 Quantum Chromodynamics [6] which are derivatives thereof. There exists,
20 however, a great resistance of these results with the theory of General Relativity
21 [7] which describes well, the tested and well verified experimental results
22 supporting the theory's foundation, namely, the Gravitational Redshift experiment
23 [8], the deflection of light experiment [9], and the accurate calculation of the
24 precession of the perihelion Mercury's orbit about the sun [10].

25 Many attempts have been made long since to bring together a theory
26 which encompasses the interaction of the discrete corpuscle, the particle, with
27 light as theorized in Maxwell's Electromagnetic Radiation (wave) Theorem [11],
28 but all have failed. Why? Why are five dimensional theories like Kaluza-Klein
29 [12] insufficient when considering all problems, but not some? Why does only
30 sometimes a theory work, but not other times, when it is the same universe we are
31 thinking, and have been thinking about? The answer is that in the mathematical
32 framework, somewhere there exists a logical discontinuity, which is hidden in the
33 mathematical ideas, which is the theory.

34 Sometimes this occurs by needing to select new coordinates from which
35 to view the problem through, or in other words, we must change our perspective
36 to see what could require a divergence from the classical relativistic viewpoint.
37 CGR here is not a full solution but rather one possible generalization of general
38 relativity so there are many things that are implied. At some point, it becomes
39 unnecessary to meticulously reframe the entirety of everything in the universe
40 because only sometimes would any such phenomena occur and sometimes can we
41 build models that are able to be verified from the implied connections to relativity
42 as well as classical mechanics. CGR end goal essentially was to build a precise
43 mathematical connection by residing QED and GR in a higher dimensional space
44 that contains both theories and define operators that can translate the information
45 from QED to GR defined through the higher dimensional space.

46 Suppose that we accept the Schrodinger interpretation [13] of QM; as we
47 must, due to the conclusive results of the theory; and as P. Dirac did, we can build
48 a relativistic theory of the electron [14]. This theory is almost satisfactory for the
49 electron, but is unable to be generalized to achieve the results of the Standard
50 Model [15]. Thus, independent of whatever individual aspect of nature we fixate
51 on, we must arrive to the experimental results of the aforementioned. If we only
52 had experimental results to consider, this endeavor would take half the time, but
53 we have also the mathematical framework which is the theory's foundation, to
54 consider. Because GR is astonishingly accurate for most cases on the
55 astrophysical level, there is no need to build from the ground up, an entirely new
56 theory which begins with a theory which matches the results of QED, and then
57 extends towards GR; in fact, this route will surely stop us in our tracks. But it
58 seems possible that there is a way to derive GR from QED by generalizing the
59 mathematical objects of QED and essentially performing the inverse operations
60 of CGR.

61 Instead, we should take the indisputable logics from the foundation of
62 Relativity, whose bases are constituent of Riemann Geometry [16], Differential
63 Geometry [17], Linear Algebra [18], Tensor Calculus [19], and the Special
64 Theory of Relativity. Now, of course SR is able to derive only a special instance
65 of relativistic Classical Mechanics, so naturally, Einstein sought the path which
66 would maximize his success, by maximizing the understanding of his notation.
67 Clearly, the notation which is used in theories like this determine the route it takes
68 to obtain a solution for problems solved with such a theoretical apparatus. This is
69 much the same as picking a certain method to solve a Rubik's cube.

70 Independent of the initial conditions of the Rubik's, or the math problem,
71 the method, the route we choose to solve, will provide the consistent result called
72 as a solution. If we are formulating a theory about the universe, inside the
73 universe, whose laws are obviously only true if there is a coherent enough
74 observer, which is the reader, or writer of the notation, we must consider that the
75 notation we use, is too, relative. This happens very obviously with the vector
76 formulation of Classical Physics, because the basis of the theory is Linear
77 Algebra, where the multiplication of the same matrix on the right versus the left,
78 actually matters. The axioms and principles of the prior can only be guaranteed
79 with the acceptance of the principles beneath even them, which go to things like
80 Algebra [20], Calculus [21], Geometry [22], etc... whose principles and axioms
81 are hinged on the truth of theorems from that of Pythagoras [23] which guarantee
82 the affine relationship of the distance traversed in a Cartesian co-ordinate system,
83 to a geometrical idea, the triangle. Now, ideas are of course a subject of
84 philosophy*, so Descartes' Five Meditations [24], which concern the concept of
85 sourcing a single true, pure fact, so to show the reason for the Sciences.

86 The first mathematical model I used to describe higher dimensional
87 spaces was the rubiks cube and defining a complex space and the complex groups
88 that correspond to the set of all possible solutions for the rubiks cube. Doing this
89 allows for one to describe essentially a rubiks cube which contains in the nxn
90 matrix case arbitrarily more entries than the Einstein field equations and QED
91 differential equations, it is clear that by defining a higher dimensional complex
92 space that is an nxn matrix, or tensor, allows for a basic form of the basis for
93 the generalized complex space that contains both of the theories.

94 The vector spaces corresponding to each of the face vectors if each face
95 has a 4 vector in space time for the rubiks cube. And describing it this way quickly
96 allows one to see that cube face vectors reside in complex space and when they
97 are all real, the rubiks cube is a cube. This is because a quarter of a quarter of a
98 third of a way through a turn, the rubiks cube for any turn is not a cube. It is almost
99 a cube, it is essentially a cube with one layer in complex space. This is the
100 definition of the cube in complex space if we assign vectors to the center of each
101 face of the rubiks cube.

102 Thus, in addition to the axioms and principles of proven mathematical
103 theorems, we shall take that there will always be something new to learn, but the
104 comprising mathematical basis remains always the same. This is the concept of
105 any science in the modern world; take for example the evolution the Carbon based
106 biomolecules into the nucleotides and nucleic acid [26] which compose the
107 Deoxyribonucleic Acid of Earth life [27]. Anything below the atomic weight of
108 Iron is able to be manufactured by the process known as fusion [28], within our
109 averaged sized Sun. The DNA replication process must thus be supplemented by
110 this theory (our theory should determine that the coagulation of particles can build
111 the sun, and then in turn, biomolecules). Darwinian evolution [29] is hinged on
112 the DNA replication process, which if our theory should be able to in some
113 extrapolation, deduce a proper model for DNA replication, we will have then,
114 mathematical evidence of Darwinian evolution. Obviously, once we include this,
115 we have succeeded with many more things than a simple model of replication, but
116 I myself have not yet taken on this task myself. I am merely stating what a good
117 theory should do.

118 The theory of Q.E.D is ever so satisfactory when it comes to the
119 mathematical formulation of experimentation. It produces consistent results.
120 What more could you ask from a theory? Well, you could ask for it to produce a
121 theory about gravity, but then, you will be working eternally, because even when
122 you find out that a unified theory is possible, you will find out immediately that
123 many things are possible (Many Worlds Interpretation [30]), like the uncovering
124 of some completely new, and apparently unrelated concept with respect to those
125 encapsulated in the prior (the universe is infinitely vast). The theory is so easy to
126 work with because it is usually in a scalar formulation, where the values of the
127 desired values of interest are determined by some scalar function of n co-
128 ordinates. This theory describes many phenomena, like that of pair production
129 [31], electron-antielectron annihilation [32], Quantum Tunneling [33], the
130 Hydrogen Atom and its constituent components [34], Compton Scattering [35],
131 so in these respects, the theory is beautiful. This is not good. We have two equally
132 wonderful descriptions of nature, which are completely opposite in nature. The
133 main opposition is that of Philosophy: we humans select, by the philosophical
134 logic of the theory, whether the interpretation should be performed, symbolically,
135 one way or another, where the main example of this is the competing of the
136 deterministic vector interpretation of GR, versus the scalar valued analysis that
137 QM usually deals with. From the theory of Q.E.D that we can take for certain is
138 the experimental evidence, the proven mathematics used, the axioms which have
139 mathematical proof, and the apparent wave nature of particles. We cannot take
140 the philosophies of Q.E.D due to the obvious contradictions that occur when
141 fitting this theory to the Heavenly bodies, and on the level of Classical Mechanics
142 (this statement becomes false if the theory is properly modified to be both
143 philosophically and mathematically conclusive). Now, philosophy in the respect
144 I speak is non speculative. I am implying Logic [36], but I say philosophy because

145 that is fundamentally what logic (and mathematics which is compactified logic by
146 symbols) is. As long as the facts are true, we may not dispute them until they are
147 untrue.

148 We know well both GR and Q.E.D, but which theory needs rectified?
149 Which theory should serve as our mathematical basis? Certainly a good QFT
150 should be able to readily match the precession of Mercury's orbit because planets
151 are composed of quantum mechanical interactions, so our theory, by deduction
152 has to start at understanding the tiny world. It would be an assumption to say that
153 "the planets are composed of atoms, so the atoms must be composed of planets,"
154 for which we are not granted certainty, so, to be the most certain about our results,
155 our theory must begin with the tiny aspects of life, and then those subtleties must
156 craft the image we hold on; "reality," the wholesome consideration; the
157 knowledge that there exists millions of languages, on Earth alone, just to describe
158 the happenings of everyday life. The theory must have both a scalar valued
159 interpretation, and a vector description, and the manipulation of the symbols in
160 our theory must follow a set of laws. These laws, themselves are the laws of
161 Nature. This can occur with the insertion of Complex Analysis [37] as the Number
162 system at basis of Relativity.

163 Of course, we should be able to derive the concepts of Hydrodynamics
164 like that of the Naiver-Stokes equations [38] and the Laws of Thermodynamics
165 [39], so a good verification is that this generalizable tool is able to make good
166 enough sense to solve problems in these fields, as in S.T.E.M related fields, like
167 Electrical Engineering. Thus, our theory should too include problems like finding
168 the current of a multi-phase circuit which is constituent of transistors [40] which
169 were predicted by Shockley's quantum theory, L.E.Diodes, capacitors, generators,
170 inductors or even simple resistors. We need to first devise the logical network of
171 thought, the mathematical framework.

172 If we can derive the field equations of Q.E.D with this theory, it will
173 suffice for the Quantum and Electromagnetic phenomena, and if we can derive
174 also field equations of GR with this theory we will have a unified theory, because
175 both of these fields encapsulate the big and the small. We must be able to extend
176 the understanding of these symbols to derive the results of the Standard Model,
177 and our theory must agree with "new" information because both "new" and "old"
178 information are relative terms; even though the Laws of Mechanics are forever
179 the same, new knowledge can be uncovered. New information is not what moves
180 forward the wheels of our collective human endeavor, it is the eradication of our
181 ignorance. The laws are set in stone; the universe is infinitely vast; it can be
182 everything we think, for the fact that we can imagine it, it could happen; we are
183 forever ignorant, but because we are forever bound at the soul by the Postulates
184 of Geometry and Mechanics, we can learn new information. We can change as a
185 species, but we need to know that we too, our philosophies, policies, social rules,
186 and everything else are relative, not just are the Heavenly Bodies.

187 The initial ideas of CGR are essentially useless since better forms of
188 CGR exist and CGR does not answer the question of field unification although it
189 begins that journey. It appears as though CGR is not needed to solve the dark
190 matter problem [43]. A Unified Field Theory [44] should be supplemented by
191 large experimental physics databases and information generally within STEM.
192 Likewise a UFT should be supported by respective technologies such as magnetic
193 field control [45] is relative to electrodynamics [46] there should be the ability for

194 the other fields, i.e strong field and electroweak fields to be supported by
195 technologies that depend on these forces of nature. Understanding how to control
196 the fields begins the task of being able to build useful and new technologies that
197 rely on these fields in a dependable way.

198

199 *Plato's Five Dialogues [25]

200 § 2

201 **Formulation of the Multidimensional Mathematical Structure for CGR**

202 A theory about the universe is written on paper, by a writer, at a particular
203 instance of time inside the Universe. I am that writer in this instant, and I am
204 aware that to teach to someone to the best of my ability, these thought about the
205 Universe, I must give information to the reader about the spatial and temporal
206 location of my perception of reality when I write about this, so that it is easier for
207 the reader to see why I selected this particular route of derivation.

208 The language used henceforth is from:

209 1) "On The Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies," Albert Einstein 1905
210 [47], and understood at least the Kinematical portion.

211 2) "The Foundation of the General Theory Relativity," By A. Einstein
212 [48] to at least § 8.

213 This paper essentially assumes the existence of a generalized derivative
214 operator [49] in time that can be converted to complex spaces [50]. By repeated
215 application of the chain rule [51] similar to that described within my taylor
216 expansion paper [52], we can arrive to the general equations that relate the
217 positions of any two observers essentially by generalizing the metric rule. It has
218 come to my attention in recent times that this approach to generalizing the spaces
219 is maybe not the best approach but nonetheless it gives an idea for what is
220 happening. Papers that should be referred to is from albert Einstein [53] with
221 complex spaces and complex tensors [54] for generalizing relativity. I noticed that
222 by generalizing the minkowski space time metric [55] from special relativity [56],
223 the general relativity metric [57] can be obtained and generalizing the variational
224 principle [58] alone allows for the entirety from general relativity to be derived
225 from there. The definition of CGR in this paper is not the metric tensor definition
226 and therefore is probably not the best definition of CGR but one of many that
227 exist. The complex tensors defining the complex trajectory in space time as well
228 as complex energy tensor and complex space time are derived essentially through
229 generalizing with the complex operator for space time metric described within
230 this paper.

231 **An intuition for the Flat Space-Time Law for n Observers:**

232 Particularly due to the issues that most have visualizing the Tensorial
233 nature of advanced field theories, I will remain throughout this series -until we
234 develop a reasonable understanding of- using a scalar formulation of Relativity
235 (so, due to the time investment required to make for this to occur, I will omit in
236 this paper the calling of "contravariant and covariant tensors). It turns out one can
237 derive the Special Theory of Relativity (SR) by considering an event which is
238 described by a Cartesian system of co-ordinates, that is, co-ordinates which
239 maintain orthogonality with respect to one another. The important idea we used,
240 was that the space-time is numerically \mathbb{C} , even though the spatial co-ordinates

241 were defined to be \mathbb{R} . In summary, for any inertial object, the description of the
 242 co-ordinates is so that there are three orthogonal \mathbb{R} (spatial co-ordinates) which
 243 are each orthogonal to a third axis, which is itself an \mathbb{I} axis. For these inertial
 244 considerations, SR relates the co-ordinates by with the equivalence of the
 245 Interval $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - c^2t^2 = x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2 - c^2t'^2$, where $x, y, z, t \rightarrow$
 246 $x(x', y', z', t'), y(x', y', z', t'), z(x', y', z', t'), t(x', y', z', t')$, thus this implies
 247 the inverse statement $x', y', z', t' \rightarrow$
 248 $x'(x, y, z, t), y'(x, y, z, t), z'(x, y, z, t), t'(x, y, z, t)$. One may diverge here, and
 249 find how these co-ordinates are related for such a flat space, but what would be
 250 found is a set of three dimensional Lorentz transformations. In just a few steps we
 251 can make the truth of SR, the foundation of GR, by considering that yes, these
 252 equations are true for a flat perspective, but extending this flat perspective could
 253 be done by asking a specific question: what about to someone who is not inertial
 254 with respect to the inertial system described by SR? We thus add another observer
 255 who is not inertial with respect to the system K' (this notation is established by
 256 Einstein in his 1905 SR paper), and therefore not inertial with respect to the
 257 unprimed system described by K .

258 This is what we are going to think about forward going. With adding
 259 another observer, we immediately discover that by the premises of physics,
 260 everyone has a valid perspective, so maybe with respect to this third perspective,
 261 the systems K and K' are non-inertial, however, with respect to this third thinker
 262 (who may too think life is linear, in the sense that his or her co-ordinates are flat
 263 by their definition), there must be another fourth perspective which maintains still
 264 yet, the principles described by SR, so long as with respect to the third observer,
 265 the fourth observer is inertial.

266 Let us characterize an event with a space-time description. The event is
 267 nothing more than the mutual origin that the observers call an event. Select some
 268 point, any point in your conceivable realm of thought as an origin. Let this point
 269 be far separated from any interacting bodies of mass, and further let this point be
 270 absent of the presence of electromagnetic fields, with which I am implying for
 271 you to think that this point is in as empty a space you can imagine. Let now for us
 272 to describe the space around this point in the perspective K^0 , who has co-ordinates
 273 (x^0, y^0, z^0, ict^0) . Thus, the distance the neighboring point (4-D Pythagorean
 274 Theorem),

275 *Definition:*

$$ds^0 \equiv \sqrt{(dx^0)^2 + (dy^0)^2 + (dz^0)^2 + (ict^0)^2} \quad \text{Eq 1}$$

276 so that a further compactification with the sigma notation can be written;
 277 when we define the co-ordinates and interval for the zeroth particle:

$$x_\mu^0, \text{ for } \mu = 0 \rightarrow 3 \mid x_0^0 \equiv x^0, x_1^0 \equiv y^0, x_2^0 \equiv z^0, x_3^0 \equiv ict^0; \quad \text{Eq 2}$$

278

$$ds^0 \equiv \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (dx_\mu^0)^2}. \quad \text{Eq 3}$$

279 Because this point in space-time can be viewed in infinitely many ways: with
 280 respect to K^0 , there must exist infinitely many respective primed systems: ${}^v K^0$,
 281 where this reads that *vth* primed system of co-ordinates with respect to K^0 .

282 ${}^{\nu}K^0$ has co-ordinates (${}^{\nu}x^0, {}^{\nu}y^0, {}^{\nu}z^0, ic {}^{\nu}t^0$), where these observers obey the
 283 relation

284 *Definition:*

$$d {}^{\nu}s^0 \equiv \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^{\nu}x_{\mu}^0)^2}; \quad \text{Eq 4)}$$

285

$${}^{\nu}x_0^0 \equiv {}^{\nu}x^0, {}^{\nu}x_1^0 \equiv {}^{\nu}y^0, {}^{\nu}x_2^0 \equiv {}^{\nu}z^0, {}^{\nu}x_3^0 \equiv ic {}^{\nu}t^0, \quad \text{Eq 5)}$$

286 which reads in English, as: with respect to the zeroth frame of reference, the ν th
 287 observer's μ th co-ordinate is described by some "forward and back, left and right,
 288 up and down, temporal" co-ordinates.

289 The ν co-ordinates follow the flat space-time rules with respect to the
 290 zeroth frame, but this is not necessarily true for other frames K^n which are
 291 possibly non-inertial with respect to K^0 . The ν components are numbered so that
 292 arbitrarily

293 $\nu = -3$ in the ${}^{-3}K^0$ system the Quantadimension, Quantum Mechanical Forces
 294 are dominant

295 $\nu = -2$ in the ${}^{-2}K^0$ is where Atomic forces are dominant

296 $\nu = -1$ in the ${}^{-1}K^0$ system Intermolecular forces are dominant

297 $\nu = 0$ in the ${}^0K^0$ system forces of Objects are dominant, the Electodimension

298 $\nu = 1$ in the ${}^1K^0$ system the forces of Systems are dominant

299 $\nu = 2$ in the ${}^2K^0$ system the forces of Universes are dominant

300 $\nu = 3$ in the ${}^3K^0$ system MultiUniversal forces are dominant, the
 301 Astrodimension

302 This notation is written so that if we consider n observers who are
 303 defining the system in the same way that the zeroth observer has, but are not
 304 localized at the same point of space-time, their space-time Interval (from here I
 305 will call this simply the Interval) will be written henceforth as

$$ds^n = \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (dx_{\mu}^n)^2}. \quad \text{Eq 6)}$$

306 It is important to say here that it is not in general true that $ds^n =$
 307 $ds^{n-1}, ds^{n-2} \dots ds^0$. These observers use the same mathematical rules, but are
 308 situated at different places in space and time which may be accelerating and hence
 309 not flat with respect.

310 **On The 5-D Interval:**

311 In this analysis, $s^n(x^n, y^n, z^n, t^n)$ ${}^{\nu}s^n({}^{\nu}x^n, {}^{\nu}y^n, {}^{\nu}z^n, {}^{\nu}t^n)$ are 5-D surfaces,
 312 described by the integrals,

$$s^n \equiv \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (dx_\mu^n)^2}, \quad \text{Eq 7)}$$

313 , and

$${}^v s^n \equiv \int_{{}^v t_\alpha^n}^{{}^v t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^v x_\mu^n)^2}, \quad \text{Eq 8)}$$

314 The bounds of integration are with respect to the co-ordinates of interest.

315 Relating the s Functions:

316 v is a variable that is going to be colored. Black is the "ground
317 dimension" and is where things are with respect to. For example, the vector ${}^0 s_\mu^n$ is
318 a description of μ th co-ordinate for the nth Particle which is with respect to the
319 Blue observer. Adding color eliminates the need of keeping track of the various
320 primed and unprimed definition which occur.

321 SR guarantees that $|ds^0|^2 = |d {}^0 s^0|^2 = |d {}^0 s^0|^2 = |d {}^0 s^0|^2$ Which, when one
322 evaluate for s, one obtains

$$\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (dx_\mu^n)^2 = \sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^0 x_\mu^n)^2 = \sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^0 x_\mu^n)^2 = \sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^0 x_\mu^n)^2 \quad \text{Eq 9)}$$

323 Whereby, because we know that ${}^v s_\mu^n \rightarrow {}^v s_\mu^n(x_\mu^n)$, and $s_\mu^n \rightarrow$
324 $s_\mu^n({}^v s_\mu^n)$, it is deduced quickly that for the minimization of these n observers to
325 simultaneously occur, each of the individual energies are minimized.

326 *Definition:*

$$E_2({}^v s_\mu^n) = \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} E_2({}^k s_\mu^n) \quad \text{Eq 10)}$$

327

$$E_n(t) = E_1(s_\mu^n) + E_2({}^v s_\mu^n) \quad \text{Eq 11)}$$

328 *Theorem 1:* $\delta E_n(t) = 0 = \delta E_1(s_\mu^n) + \delta E_2({}^v s_\mu^n)$

329 *Proof of Theorem 1:*

330 The minimization of a representative energy, $E_n(t)$, an energy which is
331 representative of some n th observer's co-ordinates, and thus those co-ordinates'
332 time, inherently meaning that the co-ordinates, which are some function of time,
333 are in some way convoluted (in time) to produce a continuous energy, because the
334 energy is itself a function of time (Law of Conservation of Energy); $E_T \rightarrow E_T(t)$;
335 $s_\mu^n \rightarrow s_\mu^n(t^n)$, and since $t^n \rightarrow t^n({}^v t^n)$, we must therefore find that $s_\mu^n \rightarrow$
336 $s_\mu^n({}^v t^n)$; thus a parameterization of the nth observer's time will produce from
337 this that $t^n \rightarrow t^n(t)$, from which $E_1, E_2 \rightarrow E_1(t), E_2(t)$.

338 5-D functions which are continuous, and superimpose, in that, any
339 localized point on the Manifold s^0 has a Scalar-Complex value representing such,
340 is summed to a Scalar-Complex number representing the Manifold describing s^n .
341 It is thus obvious (Conservation of Energy) that some sum of all the energies
342 present should be minimized, and simultaneously maximized (see Definition of
343 Energy):

$$0 = \delta E_T = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta (s^\lambda + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} v s^\lambda) \blacksquare \quad \text{Eq 12)}$$

344 Another way to state this: If \exists minimized functions (in time) for the components
 345 of s^k , then because we may have equally chosen the initial conditions of
 346 $v s^k$, \exists extremal functions to describe the components of s^k . Lambda is a dummy
 347 index used to sum to n .

348 There exists a vector description also:

$$\delta E_T(t) = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_n(t)}{\partial s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{d s_\mu^\lambda}{dt} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_n(t)}{\partial v s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{d v s_\mu^\lambda}{dt} \quad \text{Eq 13)}$$

349 The insertion of the definition of $v s^\lambda$ and s^λ **Eq 13)** becomes:

$$0 = \delta E_T = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\lambda=0}^3 (dx_\lambda^n)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 (d {}^0 x_\mu^n)^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 14)}$$

350 This last equation may be rearranged in such a fashion to arrive you to a
 351 type of Geodesic Equation for n observers, provided one expands **Eq 14)** with
 352 The Chain-Rule:

$$0 = \delta E_T = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\lambda=0}^3 \left(\frac{dx_\lambda^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d {}^0 x_\mu^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 15)}$$

353 \forall co-ordinates, \exists functions $\epsilon \in \mathbb{C}$ which describe the trajectories and
 354 velocities of particles. So, for our vector analysis to work well in cases where our
 355 functions don't "behave well," we find that the \mathbb{I} component to the velocity of
 356 observers actually occurs from some frame of reference.

357 Performing the variation, that is, equating **Eq 13)** and **Eq 15)**:

358 *CGR Geodesic Equation*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\lambda=0}^3 \left(\frac{dx_\lambda^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d {}^0 x_\mu^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 16)} \\ & = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^n) + E_2(v s_\mu^n)}{\partial s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{d s_\mu^\lambda}{dt} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^n)}{\partial v s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{d v s_\mu^\lambda}{dt} \end{aligned}$$

359 Where we effectively learn that the change in the position of the co-
 360 ordinates in a dynamic system are characterized by the space-time the particles
 361 are defined within.

362 The $v = 0$ systems are systems with respect to the particles that are
 363 permanently flat. Positive omega imply zooming to the astrodimension and
 364 negative omega imply zooming to the quanta-dimension.

365

366 § 3

367 **The Complex Numbered Theory of General Relativity: Definitions,**
 368 **Postulates**

369 **The Postulates of CGR:**

370 **1)** The postulates of Relativity [47] (this has been previously cited, and is here for
371 the ease of reading), except where the term "gravity," appears. In those cases, we
372 need to think more generally. When one thinks of the gravitational field, where
373 the natural understanding which occurs in the mind is the analogous Electric Field.
374 In CGR, they are not called individual fields, the ideas are superimposed into a
375 single concept: objects are localized inside space-time, and these objects can
376 move within space-time. The motion of these objects, the trajectory, is described
377 by the four acceleration, where the components of the describing vector are
378 functions of the co-ordinates that the vector with. This is the case because the
379 acceleration of an object is due to the influence of another object, when either is
380 within a close enough proximity to the next. Thus, the space-time (a five
381 dimensional colored surface, which moves in time, and whose colors change in
382 time of one object, which is a function of that object's co-ordinates, must be in
383 some way relative to the next object.

384 **2)** Particles are localized at a point in space-time [59], described by three real
385 valued spatial co-ordinates and one imaginary, time component which can be
386 measured by rulers and clocks. I take the thoughts of De Broglie Bohm [42] as
387 true, which show that for QM experiments like the slit experiment, particles may
388 follow continuous mathematical paths, and still yet produce the same
389 experimental results. This becomes especially obvious when Imaginary
390 components are included to the velocities. The paths are seemingly just strange
391 because the physics on the subatomic scale needs Complex Analysis, even though
392 we humans think it is less natural.

393 **3)** Everything is relative. We may select an arbitrary point in space-time to analyze
394 from, so everything is with respect to this reference point.

395 **4)** \forall space-time co-ordinates, $\exists \mathbb{C}$ functions which describe the behavior of the
396 Particles, Atoms, Molecules, Objects, Systems, Universes, and Multiverses. In
397 CM, this is the Lagrangian, and in QM, the Hamiltonian, and in GR, the variation
398 of the Einstein Hilbert Action. In GCR, these functions are thought of as the
399 energy of the system.

400 **5)** All rigid bodies [60] are composed of Particles which are in various different
401 systematic arrangements with respect. Particles are described by co-ordinates, and
402 these co-ordinates are with respect to all other interacting particles or bodies
403 within an appreciable vicinity. In the greater scheme of things, this vicinity is all
404 of interacting space.

405 **6)** Thus due to **5)**, all of the interactions can be parameterized by a single variable,
406 t .

407 **7)** **6)** produces the requirement that with respect to t , all functions and co-ordinates
408 are continuou. The important discussion for the following statement is in the
409 previous papers: $t \in \mathbb{C}$.

410 **8)** Due to **7)**, $s \in \mathbb{C}$.

411 **9)** As shown by the section concerning the continuity condition in **2)** of **§ 1**, these
412 functions must follow the Riemann-Cauchy continuity condition.

413 *All applicable mathematical proof is accepted as the basis of the theory, so long
414 as the mathematics is defined well enough for the problem, but the most crucial
415 statement which is relevant to accepting all sorts of mathematical proof, is that
416 the symbolic description of one theory must be able to be converted into standard
417 notation of CGR*

418 The above is not a postulate, but it must be true. The notation of one
 419 theory must be able to be translated precisely into another theory. Much like "Ich
 420 bin sehr hungrig" exists in English as "I am very hungry," we should be able to
 421 translate mathematical notation with the most precision.

422 With these ideas in mind, I am going to progress further the mathematical
 423 framework of the theory, which has been previously discussed throughout this
 424 paper.

425 We have some observer localized at x, y, z, t who understands the
 426 universe with respect to his co-ordinates. These co-ordinates I will use as our "free
 427 to choose where we analyze from" co-ordinates. This observer knows that all the
 428 energy in the universe with respect to him is $E_T(x, y, z, t) = E_T(t) = \sum E_n(t)$,
 429 and thus

430 *Definition:*

$$E_T \equiv \sum_{\lambda=0}^n E_n(t). \quad \text{Eq 17)}$$

431 Performing the $\lim_{t \rightarrow t^n} x_\mu^n$ or $\lim_{t \rightarrow t^n} {}^v x_\mu^n$ we must arrive to x_μ^n and ${}^v x_\mu^n$,
 432 respectively. From the t location, however, \exists an infinite number of ways to
 433 perform this limit. Teleporting is not an option in physics. There are as of right
 434 now, n equations, and n unknowns.

435 What is left to perform the extension of Relativity, is to extend the
 436 analysis to be Complex valued. After we extend, the conformation to the Coulomb
 437 potential for two particles separated by a non-changing distance will produce the
 438 results of QED.

439 *Proof:* $E_T \in \mathbb{C}$

440 $x_\mu^n \rightarrow x_\mu^n(t) \mid \text{if } t \in \mathbb{C}, \Rightarrow x_\mu^n \in \mathbb{C};$

441 *Thus,* $\Rightarrow {}^v x_\mu^n \in \mathbb{C}, \text{ and } E_T \in \mathbb{C} \blacksquare$

442 The variation of E_T will provide us with a Complex set of field equations.
 443 If the following derivative operators are generalized this is representation is
 444 equivalent to performing the variation of the action where the action is a Total
 445 Energy function.

446 *Definition: CGR Field Equations*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} &= 0 \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{dE_T}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 18)}$$

447 Note that \exists a primed set of equations because of the symmetry of the
 448 theory. By the postulates of Relativity, the creation of the t observer requires the
 449 creation of a t' observer, so that

450 $ds^2(x, y, z, t) = ds^2(x', y', z', t').$

451 Whereby, our plane of possibilities expand. I will denote ${}^v_n x_\mu$ to
 452 represent the t' primed co-ordinates | for $\mu = 0 \rightarrow 3$, ${}^v_0 x_0 = ic_0^v t'$, ${}^v_0 x_1 =$
 453 ${}^v_0 x'$, ${}^v_0 x_2 = {}^v_0 y'$, ${}^v_0 x_3 = {}^v_0 z'$,

454 Where if we let for nu to be zero, we can localize the primed system and
 455 the unprimed at a mutual origin. The co-ordinates with the lower left hand

456 subscript should be understood as the equivalent definitions for the co-ordinates
 457 with the lower right, except with respect to t' and not t . With these prior
 458 considerations, symmetry forces us to update the Geodesic Equation which is
 459 trivial. The new energy condition is

460 *Definition:*

$$E_T \equiv E_T(t) + E_T(t'). \quad \text{Eq 19)}$$

461 If now, we perform the minimization of E_T on **{L(814)}**, I find the most
 462 general Geodesic Equation we can for now consider:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t'_a}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{dx_{\mu}^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t'_a}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d^0 x_{\mu}^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t'_a}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d_{\lambda} x_{\mu}}{dt} dt \right)^2} \right. \\ & \quad + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t'_a}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d_{\lambda}^0 x_{\mu}}{dt} dt \right)^2} \\ & = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1(s_{\mu}^{\lambda}) + E_2({}^v s_{\mu}^{\lambda})}{\partial s_{\mu}^{\lambda}} \frac{d s_{\mu}^{\lambda}}{dt} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_1(s_{\mu}^{\lambda})}{\partial {}^v s_{\mu}^{\lambda}} \frac{d {}^v s_{\mu}^{\lambda}}{dt'} \\ & \quad + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1({}_{\lambda} s_{\mu}) + E_2({}_{\lambda} s_{\mu})}{\partial {}_{\lambda} s_{\mu}} \frac{d {}_{\lambda} s_{\mu}}{dt'} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_1({}_{\lambda} s_{\mu})}{\partial {}_{\lambda} s_{\mu}} \frac{d {}_{\lambda} s_{\mu}}{dt'} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 20)}$$

463 To now address the Complex portion: the sole condition of this theory is
 464 logical continuity, so we are going to keep applying these thoughts until we come
 465 to the most general set of equations that we possibly can. Once we come to the
 466 most general equations that a particle can obey, all we must do is conform our
 467 apparatus to the simplest case a particle might find itself in (and to my mind this
 468 is the Coulomb force), and then solve for the variables.

469 Given that ${}^v x_{\mu}^n \rightarrow {}^v x_{\mu}^n(x_{\mu}^n)$,

470 And given further that ${}^v_n x_{\mu} \rightarrow {}^v_n x_{\mu} ({}_n x_{\mu})$,

471 we see that for ${}^v_n x_{\mu} \rightarrow {}^v_n x_{\mu} (t)$, the converse must be true, in that

472 ${}^v x_{\mu}^n \rightarrow {}^v x_{\mu}^n(t')$. In effect, we have, then:

$$473 E_T \rightarrow E_T(t', t) = E_T({}^v_n x_{\mu}, {}^v x_{\mu}^n, {}_n x_{\mu}, x_{\mu}^n)$$

474 With respect to the observer x, y, z, t , who only thinks in 4-d, we have a 5-d Scalar
 475 Theory, which can thus far be described well with the techniques discussed in **1.0)**
 476 of § 1.

477 The co-ordinates may be highly nonlinear so we ought not to wait to extend the
 478 analysis: even the constituent co-ordinates may take on Complex values. With
 479 considering this, I propose a way to encapsulate this in the notation:

$$480 {}^v x_{\mu}^n = {}^v u_{\mu}^n + i {}^v v_{\mu}^n,$$

$$481 x_{\mu}^n = u_{\mu}^n + i v_{\mu}^n,$$

$$482 {}^v_n x_{\mu} = {}^v_n u_{\mu} + i {}^v_n v_{\mu},$$

$$483 {}_n x_{\mu} = {}_n u_{\mu} + i {}_n v_{\mu}.$$

484 The imaginary velocities imply negative energy, where such matter
 485 terms seem likely to be the missing terms responsible for the Dark Energy
 486 problem.

487 As of right now, the summarization of CGR occurs in three statements:

488 **Eq 21)** *Generalized Polynomial Representation of Interval: Simplest Polynomial*
 489 *expansion is Taylor expansion*

490 Here, $s = {}^0_0s_0^0$

$$\begin{aligned}
 491 \quad & \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k(-1)^k \frac{d^{-k-1}s(t)}{dt}}{(t-t_1)^{k+1}} \right] \\
 492 \quad & + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k(-1)^k \frac{d^{-k-1}s(t')}{dt'}}{(t'-t'_1)^{k+1}} \right] \\
 493 \quad & = s(t_1) \ln(t_2 - t_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(t-t_1)^k \frac{d^k s(t)}{dt^k}}{k(k!)} \right] \\
 494 \quad & + s(t'_1) \ln(t'_2 - t'_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(t'-t'_1)^k \frac{d^k s(t')}{dt'^k}}{k(k!)} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

495 **Eq 22)** *CGR Field Equations (applying generalized derivative operator to total*
 496 *system energy):*

$$\begin{aligned}
 497 \quad & \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \frac{dE_T}{dt'} = 0 \\
 498 \quad & = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \frac{dE_T}{dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{dE_T}{dt}
 \end{aligned}$$

499 **Eq 23)** *CGR Geodesic Equations: Variation of generalized space-time interval:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 500 \quad & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{dx_\mu^n}{dt} \right)^2} \right) \\
 501 \quad & + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d {}^0x_\mu^n}{dt} \right)^2} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d {}^\lambda x_\mu}{dt} \right)^2} \right) \\
 502 \quad & + \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \int_{t_\alpha^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d {}^\lambda x_\mu}{dt} \right)^2} \\
 503 \quad & = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda)}{\partial s_\mu^\lambda} + E_2({}^v s_\mu^\lambda) \frac{ds_\mu^\lambda}{dt} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda)}{\partial {}^v s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{d {}^v s_\mu^\lambda}{dt'} \\
 504 \quad & + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1({}^\lambda s_\mu)}{\partial {}^\lambda s_\mu} + E_2({}^v s_\mu) \frac{d {}^\lambda s_\mu}{dt'} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \sum_{v=0}^{v=k} \sum_{k=0}^{k=v} \frac{\partial E_1({}^\lambda s_\mu)}{\partial {}^\lambda s_\mu} \frac{d {}^\lambda s_\mu}{dt'}
 \end{aligned}$$

505 Each point in space-time is defined by a world line.

506 $\quad \quad \quad {}^v s_\mu^n \rightarrow {}^v s_\mu^n(t), \text{ and } {}^v_n s_\mu \rightarrow {}^v_n s_\mu(t')$

507 But, because $t', t \rightarrow t'(t), t(t')$,

508 $\quad \quad \quad \Rightarrow {}^v s_\mu^n \rightarrow {}^v s_\mu^n(t, t'), \text{ and } {}^v_n s_\mu \rightarrow {}^v_n s_\mu(t', t).$

509 So, for a vector analysis, we define the four four-vectors which exist for an n
510 particle analysis:

$$\begin{aligned} \overrightarrow{s_\mu^n(t, t')} &= \begin{pmatrix} u_0^n + i v_0^n \\ u_1^n + i v_1^n \\ u_2^n + i v_2^n \\ u_3^n + i v_3^n \end{pmatrix}, \quad \overrightarrow{{}^v s_\mu^n(t, t')} = \begin{pmatrix} {}^v u_0^n + i {}^v v_0^n \\ {}^v u_1^n + i {}^v v_1^n \\ {}^v u_2^n + i {}^v v_2^n \\ {}^v u_3^n + i {}^v v_3^n \end{pmatrix} \\ \overrightarrow{{}^v_n s_\mu(t', t)} &= \begin{pmatrix} {}^v_n u_0 + i {}^v_n v_0 \\ {}^v_n u_1 + i {}^v_n v_1 \\ {}^v_n u_2 + i {}^v_n v_2 \\ {}^v_n u_3 + i {}^v_n v_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \overrightarrow{{}_n s_\mu(t', t)} = \begin{pmatrix} {}_n u_0 + i {}_n v_0 \\ {}_n u_1 + i {}_n v_1 \\ {}_n u_2 + i {}_n v_2 \\ {}_n u_3 + i {}_n v_3 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 24)}$$

511 Thus, if we look at the description of the space-time in scalar form
512 instead with a vector description,

$$\langle E_T \rangle_\mu \rightarrow E_T \left(\overrightarrow{s_\mu^n(t, t')}, \overrightarrow{{}^v s_\mu^n(t, t')}, \overrightarrow{{}_n s_\mu(t', t)}, \overrightarrow{{}^v_n s_\mu(t', t)} \right), \quad \text{Eq 25)}$$

513 we can produce a Matrix [61] $\langle E_T \rangle$, with four directions (μ), which is in some
514 way determined by the problem constructed with the four vectors. We will search
515 for this multidimensional matrix of information in the next section.

516 The Vector Analysis and Scalar Analysis must equate:

$$E_T(t', t, {}^v_n u_\mu, {}^v_n v_\mu, {}^v u_\mu^n, {}^v v_\mu^n, {}_n u_\mu, {}_n v_\mu, u_\mu^n, v_\mu^n) - \langle E_T \rangle_\mu = 0 \quad \text{Eq 26)}$$

517 This was before I knew about complex metric tensors and the
518 generalizations from einsteins theory. More simply, the geodesic equations [62]
519 of Einsteins theory have extra terms.

520 § 3.1

521 CGR Field and Geodesic Equations

522 The next step is to find equation 4, the differential general differential
523 equation. The motivation for this comes from the dimensionality spawns in the
524 analysis of the Riemann zeta function [63] as an energy function. It is unlike any
525 energy considered in physics thus far, and so we must guarantee that the roots are
526 unique.

527 First, we recognize that through the employment of Taylor Expansion on
528 $Z(s)$, we obtain the double sum:

$$Z(s) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k (s - s_0)^k \ln^k(s_0)}{k! n^{s_0}}; \quad \text{Eq 27)}$$

529 Let s_j the j th zero of $Z(s)$ so that $Z(s_j) = 0$. Taylor's Theorem requires
530 only continuity, which is ensured by the existence of the k th derivative of n^{-s} . In
531 defining T roots, we can seek to expand with the same algorithm by operating
532 Taylor's Theorem on n^{s_2} with respect to the s_2 th zero:

$$Z(s) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k_0} (-1)^{k_1} (s - s_0)^{k_0} (s_0 - s_1)^{k_2} \ln^{k_0}(s_1) \ln^{k_1}(s_1)}{k_0! k_1! n^{s_2}} \quad \text{Eq 28)$$

533 It is clear that if we repeat this algorithm T times, we arrive to:

$$Z(s) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^T \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right) \quad \text{Eq 29)$$

534 It immediately follows that the sum $1^{-s} + 2^{-s} \dots$ can be written as a
 535 polynomial whose coefficients are determined by the roots. The roots thus are
 536 Unique because of the product expression for $Z(s)$ through the Euler Product.

537 We have, a working definition, that with respect to a 4-D observer with
 538 co-ordinates, x, y, z, t , on paper, that could be understood in five dimensions with
 539 respect to me, who is writing on 2-D, I had to implement color so to provide for
 540 the missing dimension, otherwise the descriptions become brutal. If we consider
 541 the Quantum Realm, to be infinitely small, the notation which is black is the most
 542 basic, the simple origin, selected as colorless.

543 Let us go in the negative direction of time, 13.7 billion Earth years to
 544 imagine the happenings of the Big Bang [64]. Imagine for us to be localized in a
 545 region always outside of the expansion, so that we may observe this happening
 546 without being within. One may run difficulty with such a problem because if we
 547 might suppose nothing other than the dramatic explosion of the singularity [65]
 548 exists in the universe, which is the only assumption we are rightfully justified in
 549 making, to be forever outside the universe, would require for us to be "zooming"
 550 outward. This magnification is a co-ordinate transformation of the universe's
 551 original co-ordinates which were once infinitely small, but are now, with respect
 552 to us within the universe, are clearly on a different number scale entirely, because
 553 of how large the objects respectively are. This idea of "zoom" provides a way to
 554 see how the numerical values of respective galactic scales, and quantum scales,
 555 will change, when we want to understand the physics on one of these "levels" and
 556 apply it to an entirely different numerical scale, or "level." To do this without at
 557 some point breaking the second postulate of Special Relativity, would be
 558 impossible. This thought experiment, to occur, must be moving through
 559 dimensions. The definition of Zoom is in the Additional Information section.

560 Let us define a general differential equation for the analysis We will then
 561 have a symmetric set of equations to work with.

562 *Definition: General Differential Equation for an Object: to find systems,*
 563 *Universes, we simple need to sum the systems or Universes symmetrically to*
 564 *produce the new general equation. Rigid Objects Equation:*

$$E_{TDE} = \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{\mu=0}^3 f_k \left(f_{\lambda} \left(f_{\mu} \left(\lambda^{k\lambda_{\mu}}, \frac{d^{\alpha} \lambda^{0\lambda_{\mu}}}{dt^{\alpha}} \lambda^{x_{\mu}}, \frac{d^n \lambda^{x_{\mu}}}{dt^n}, {}^0 x_{\mu}^{\lambda}, \frac{d^{\alpha} {}^0 x_{\mu}^{\lambda}}{dt^{\alpha}}, x_{\mu}^n, \frac{d^{\alpha} x_{\mu}^{\lambda}}{dt^{\alpha}}, x, x', y, y', z, z', t, t' \right) \right) \right) + \sum_{-\lambda=0}^{-n} \sum_{-k=0}^{-v} \sum_{-v=0}^{-k} \sum_{-k=0}^{-v} \sum_{-3}^{-\mu=0} f_{\bar{k}} \left(f_{\bar{\lambda}} \left(f_{\bar{\mu}} \left(\bar{\lambda}^{k\bar{\lambda}_{\mu}}, \frac{d^{\alpha} \bar{\lambda}^{0\bar{\lambda}_{\mu}}}{dt^{\alpha}} \bar{\lambda}^{x_{\mu}}, \frac{d^n \bar{\lambda}^{x_{\mu}}}{dt^n}, {}^0 x_{\mu}^{\bar{\lambda}}, \frac{d^{\alpha} {}^0 x_{\mu}^{\bar{\lambda}}}{dt^{\alpha}}, x_{\mu}^n, \frac{d^{\alpha} x_{\mu}^{\bar{\lambda}}}{dt^{\alpha}}, x, x', y, y', z, z', t, t' \right) \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 30)$$

565 We have a set of unique root equations, differential equations, field equations and
 566 geodesic equations for the analysis. We have $cdt = ds$, and $|ds^0|^2 = |d_0^0 s|^2 =$
 567 $|d_0^0 s|^2 = |d_0^0 s|^2$.

568 The apparatus of CGR is thus: **1) = 2) = 3) = 4)** :

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{\mu=0}^3 f_k \left(f_\lambda \left(f_\mu \left(\lambda x_\mu, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu}{dt^\alpha}, \lambda x_\mu, \frac{d^n \lambda x_\mu}{dt^n}, {}^0 x_\mu, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu^\lambda}{dt^\alpha}, x_\mu^n, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu^\lambda}{dt^\alpha}, x, x', y, y', z, z', t' \right) \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 31)} \\
 = & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_1^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{dx_\mu^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} \right. \\
 & + \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \int_{t_1^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d^\alpha x_\mu^n}{dt} dt \right)^2} - \left(\sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda) + E_2({}^v s_\mu^\lambda)}{\partial s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{ds_\mu^\lambda}{dt} \right. \\
 & \left. + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda) d {}^v s_\mu^\lambda}{\partial {}^v s_\mu^\lambda} dt' \right) \\
 = & \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k(-1)^k \frac{d^{k-1} s(t)}{dt}}{(t-t_1)^{k+1}} \right] - \left(s(t_1) \ln(t_2 - t_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(t-t_1)^k \frac{d^k s(t)}{dt^k}}{k(k!)} \right] \right) \\
 = & \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial x} \frac{dt}{dt} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial y} \frac{dt}{dt} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial z} \frac{dt}{dt} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial t} \frac{dt}{dt} = 0 = \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial x'} \frac{dt'}{dt'} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial y'} \frac{dt'}{dt'} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial z'} \frac{dt'}{dt'} + \frac{\partial dE_T}{\partial t'} \frac{dt'}{dt'} \\
 & = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k(-1)^k \frac{d^{k-1} s(t')}{dt'}}{(t'-t'_1)^{k+1}} \right] \right) - \left(s(t'_1) \ln(t'_2 - t'_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(t'-t'_1)^k \frac{d^k s(t')}{dt'^k}}{k(k!)} \right] \right) \\
 & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda) + E_2({}^v s_\mu^\lambda)}{\partial s_\mu^\lambda} \frac{ds_\mu^\lambda}{dt} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \frac{\partial E_1(s_\mu^\lambda) d {}^v s_\mu^\lambda}{\partial {}^v s_\mu^\lambda} dt' \\
 & - \left(\sum_{\lambda=0}^n \delta \left(\int_{t_1^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d^\alpha x_\mu}{dt} dt \right)^2} + \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \int_{t_1^n}^{t^n} \sqrt{\sum_{\mu=0}^3 \left(\frac{d^\alpha x_\mu}{dt} dt \right)^2} \right) \right) \\
 = & \sum_{\lambda=0}^n \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{v=0}^k \sum_{k=0}^v \sum_{\mu=0}^3 f_k \left(f_\lambda \left(f_\mu \left(\lambda x_\mu, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu}{dt^\alpha}, \lambda x_\mu, \frac{d^n \lambda x_\mu}{dt^n}, {}^0 x_\mu, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu^\lambda}{dt^\alpha}, x_\mu^n, \frac{d^\alpha x_\mu^\lambda}{dt^\alpha}, x, x', y, y', z, z', t' \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

569 In effect, CGR is a system of equations that contains all dynamical information
 570 about the system with relative energy functions.

571 § 3.2)

572 Imaginary Interpretation of Riemann's Hypothesis

573 Analyzing ζ calls for essentially all the same rules for the underlying functions
 574 that the function was derived from which is essentially Z since analytic
 575 continuation of Z transforms the function into ζ . Considering further the concept
 576 of imagining zeta functions: if we carefully select x' , we can find a function which
 577 has zeros precisely at The Zeta function's zeros, but is not equivalent to The Zeta
 578 function anywhere else. Here, we are going to find a function which *is* this
 579 balancing energy: the easiest selection of x' which comes to mind is something
 580 like viewing the zeta-Energy upside-down. When we do this, we can easily find
 581 an equation which is only true at the zeros of The Zeta function because we can
 582 use the statement of the

583 Conservation of zeta-Energy:

$$\frac{dZ}{dt} - \frac{dZ}{dt} = 0, \quad \text{Eq 32)}$$

584 and make it false everywhere except where the zeros occur. This zero equation
585 can read

586 *Untrue Conservation of zeta-Energy Equation; zeta zero condition:*

$$\frac{dZ}{dt} + \frac{dZ}{dt} = 0. \quad \text{Eq 33)}$$

587 If one can find a function which mirrors the zeta function such that the
588 intersection of this new function (which is equal to the root of negative one into
589 the zeta-Energy) and The Zeta function only occur at the zeros of The Zeta
590 function and after to set up an inequality everywhere except at the zeros (where
591 the inequality becomes an equality) one can find the necessary condition for The
592 Riemann-Zeta Function's zeros. In other words, if one were to set up an equation
593 which is everywhere false, except at The Riemann zeros, and one can further find
594 the places where the equation becomes true, one will find the only places zeros
595 can possibly occur in The \mathbb{C} plane.

596 Z' ($-Z$) is a function of some other co-ordinates, we may call as the primed
597 co-ordinates.

598 We may select for the x' co-ordinates to have a trajectory which is \mathbb{I} when x is
599 \mathbb{R} (having an \mathbb{I} velocity). Although the x and x' coordinates seem to be completely
600 nonrealistic, perhaps not too dissimilar to solving the cube in the mirror (and
601 imagining co-ordinates at the center of mirror you, you, and the Rubik's), and both
602 mirror you, and you understand life to be exactly opposite of one another, both of
603 you will come to the same conclusion after the cube is solved in m moves;
604 specifically, that the cube is solved.

605 The equation $1 = 1$ is always true. The equation $1 = i$ is never true.

606 With rewriting the exponential function;

$$n^{-ict} = e^{-ict \ln(n)}, n^{-(x+ict)} = n^{-x} \cos(ct \ln(n)) - in^{-x} \sin(ct \ln(n)); \quad \text{Eq 34)}$$

607 as so, one will find that The Zeta Function is easily separated into \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{I}
608 parts. $\Rightarrow Z(x + ict) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(ct \ln(n)) - i \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(ct \ln(n))$. To
609 find the function which has the same zeros as The Zeta Function, but has a
610 negative value for The Zeta Function everywhere that The Zeta Function exists is
611 to find a function which I call as opposite to The Zeta Function. Given that; The
612 Zeta-Energy follows the Extremal Energy Condition of Physics (this is
613 representative of Newton's Equations being derived from the Euler Minimization
614 of a representative Lagrange Energy), $|Z$, (which is a sum from $n = 1$ to $n =$
615 ∞ , of n raised to the complex variable, $(x + ict)$, is parameterized by the variable
616 t ; the same statement occurs for the primed viewer of the primed zeta function,
617 which is a function of the primed observers time; which can be written more
618 compactly as $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x(x',t')} \cos(ct(x',t') \ln(n)) -$
619 $i \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x(x',t')} \sin(ct(x',t') \ln(n))$.

620 One must be able to find that in some frame, some selection of co-ordinates,
621 the functions Z and Z' must be related. The interval principle which bounds the
622 happenings of the primed coordinates to the unprimed co-ordinates for Cartesian
623 spaces tell us how these functions can be related. Given that (x, ict) , (x', ict') are
624 two different co-ordinate happenings which are observing the same event (the
625 event here is given by the zeta-Energy), they (the co-ordinates) must follow the
626 space-time equivalence principle (interval principle), so that the co-ordinates

627 (they can understand one another) are functions of each other; that is, the primed
 628 co-ordinates are functions of the unprimed, and vice-versa; which is concisely
 629 written as: Given that $dx^2 - c^2 dt^2 = dx'^2 - c^2 dt'^2 \mid x', ict' \rightarrow$
 630 $x'(x, t), t'(x, t); \Rightarrow f(x + ict) = x' + ict'$, due to the continuity requirement.
 631 Imagine that the unprimed observers are restricted to the \mathbb{R} numbers, while the
 632 primed co-ordinates can be themselves \mathbb{C} .

633 The transformed to interval, and the originally primed interval can be obtained
 634 from the multivariate chain rule: With three spatial co-ordinates, and the
 635 assumption that the primed coordinates are not always orthogonal to one another,
 636 one can receive the displacement interval from GR suggested by Gauss $ds^2 =$
 637 $g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$. Selecting an Opposite Zeta Function \mid the Taylor Expansion of this
 638 Opposite Zeta Function yields a negative sign before the odd numbered nth
 639 derivative. This is an important selection because the extremal values of the
 640 Opposite Zeta Function have the same magnitude as one another, but opposite
 641 total value. \Rightarrow that the zeros are located at the same location by the Extreme Value
 642 Theorem of Calculus. Written again with The Energy to be a function of the co-
 643 ordinates,

644 *Zeta-Zero Equation:*

$$Z(x + ict) + Z'(x' + ict') = 0 \tag{Eq 35}$$

645 Henceforth, we will imagine analyzing The Zeta-Energy from the unprimed
 646 co-ordinates along only the \mathbb{R} axis, so that with the unprimed observer (who isn't
 647 thinking about \mathbb{I} numbers) is still watching The Zeta Energy, but the primed
 648 observer who has to consider imaginary units is too watching the dynamic,
 649 imaginary, Zeta Energy. There is no need to restrict x' and t' to the \mathbb{R} variables;
 650 in fact, it will limit us to do so.

651 Where with this prior image, one may set $t = 0$, after recognizing that then,
 652 with respect to x , one is analyzing the forward valued function (The Euler Sum),
 653 the function that someone who can't perceive \mathbb{C} numbers would see, while we, the
 654 creatures who can view \mathbb{C} co-ordinates inquire about the zeros of this \mathbb{C} function.
 655 Written symbolically, $Z(x) + Z'(x'(x) + ict'(x)) = 0; \Rightarrow$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} + Z' = 0. \tag{Eq 36}$$

656 The Zeta-Zero Equation is only obeyed at the zeros of The Zeta function.
 657 Certainly, the \mathbb{R} parts and \mathbb{I} parts must simultaneously equate. This proof requires
 658 that The Riemann-Zeta function diverges for x bigger than one (when traversing
 659 along the real axis with $t = 0$). Supposing that one considers functions for x
 660 prime (perhaps for example one considers that the x prime creature is a creature
 661 who views the x co-ordinate as having mathematically opposite coordinates to
 662 theirs), one may argue that by knowing the primed (complex valued) co-ordinates
 663 are still yet functions of the x coordinate even with t equal to zero. Once traversing
 664 along the $\mathbb{R}(x)$ number line with a parameter (in our case letting t be the variable
 665 which bounds the individual graphs), one can find a visual interpretation for why
 666 the zeros occur where they do on the x number line. Supposing that Complex
 667 numbers are important in Physical analysis; when deriving the Lorentz
 668 Transformations supposing that the constants which bound the primed and
 669 unprimed coordinates are not actually just Real valued; it is easy to see why Dirac
 670 encouraged negative energies, and the antiparticle. Antiparticles are seemingly
 671 just particles with inverse valued velocities [66]. If one considers life from the
 672 \mathbb{I} world; the alternate realm which stabilizes ours: something like $x' = ix$ (from
 673 the interval principle) one can find that the previous condition can also be written
 674 in another way that will allow one to receive the zero condition for the x co-

675 ordinates. This last assertion has that $x'^2 = -x^2$, so that as you are a primed
 676 creature who has the distance equal to one unit, the unprimed sees the exact same
 677 distance, but in the opposite of the primed observer.

678 Lorentz had found that in order to agree on reality (when the observers
 679 feel no force, and are hence not accelerating), when the respective velocity
 680 between these two is significant enough, these two observers can imagine life
 681 from one another's perspective having to obey the relations: $t' = \gamma \left(t - \frac{vx}{c^2} \right)$, and
 682 $x' = \gamma(x - vt)$ [67]. For the understanding of the x , and t co-ordinates by primed
 683 observer, because with respect to the primed observer, everything may well be
 684 with respect to him, just as much as the problem depends on them, they might
 685 consider that they are thinking about him too: $t = \gamma(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2})$, $x = \gamma(x' + vt')$.
 686 Hermann Minkowski, Carl Friedrich Gauss, and especially Bernhard Riemann
 687 each suggested several times the usage of imaginary numbers in their theoretical
 688 framework of the world, so, here, when analyzing a spatial event in one
 689 dimension, we will define a two vector, for the observers with the first (\mathbb{I}
 690 component) denoting the time component, and a real component which describes
 691 the spatial distance.

692 Because this function is representative of an energy function, the Law of
 693 Conservation of Energy [68] must be obeyed, so that:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-(x+ict)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-(\gamma(x' + vt') + i c\gamma(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}))} \quad \text{Eq 37}$$

694 Now that we have a condition which must be obeyed by these two
 695 observers (who have a relative velocity, and whose co-ordinates are bonded
 696 together), the following equation is never true except when the energy functions
 697 intersect. The intersections are at the zeros only, as guaranteed by the energy
 698 minimization principles by Euler and Lagrange [69], for Physics requires
 699 minimization in time. The Zeta Energy Zero Condition becomes:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-(x+ict)} = i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-(\gamma(x' + vt') + i c\gamma(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}))} \quad \text{Eq 38}$$

700 With $t' = it$, and $x = x'$ to travel a single unit in time for the
 701 imaginary particle. It's like going one unit in inverse time: the spatial distance the
 702 functions meet is half way. The squaring of t makes $-t'$.

$$\cos(\pi x) + i \sin(\pi x) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-n)^{-x} n^{ict} = - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-(\gamma(x' + vt') + i c\gamma(t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}))} \quad \text{Eq 40}$$

703 § 3.3)

704 **Thought Experiment: Creation of an Imaginary Cartesian Complex -**
 705 **Numbered Space-Time for Elimination of Mathematical Singularities in GR;**
 706 **Findings: A Generalizable Analytical Method to Translate Scientific Papers;**
 707 **Application to B. Riemann's 1859 Manuscript to Maximize Understanding**
 708 **of Variables and Prove Riemann's Hypothesis**

709 This whole section is a side by side derivation with Riemann's 1859
 710 Manuscript. When I introduce new variable, Riemann has in his paper. This
 711 manuscript is available in the Additional Information section about Riemann's
 712 Hypothesis.

713 The Euler-Product Relation can be derived from repeated factorization
 714 of the sum of n raised to a power, s . Our language is Physics, so we must consider
 715 a second primed observer, for reasons of symmetry.

$$\prod_{\text{prime } \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}} \quad \text{Eq 41)}$$

716 I will define the expressions $Z(s)$ and $Z'(s')$, for the left and right side
 717 of **Eq 41**), respectively. We define the variables s and s' with respect to the zeta
 718 function we have selected.

$$\begin{aligned} s &= x + ct \mid x, t \in \mathbb{C}. Z(s) = \infty \forall \Re(s) > 1; & \text{Eq 42)} \\ s' &= x' + ict' \mid x', t' \in \mathbb{C}. Z(s') = \infty \forall \Re(s') > 1. \end{aligned}$$

719 This definition occurs because

720 $Z(s) = Z'(s')$ is true at least when $\Re(s) > 1, \Re(s') > 1$.

721 Because we have a primed observer, which we have not yet strictly
 722 defined, but is in some way related to the unprimed observer, there is a
 723 relationship which must exist between the primed and unprimed variables. I will
 724 keep it throughout the derivation. We may rescale this number to 1, later, and it
 725 will not affect the outcome.

726 After this definition, because it is in the title of his manuscript, it is clear
 727 that Riemann wishes to count the prime numbers. Riemann looks to understand
 728 the nature of the sum of n^{-s} . Thus, we look for two functions $n^s, n^{s'}$ which obey
 729 the same rules:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(n\sigma)} \sigma^{s'-1} d\sigma &= \frac{\prod(s' - 1)}{n^{s'}}, & \text{Eq 43)} \\ \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(n\sigma)} \sigma^{s-1} d\sigma &= \frac{\prod(s - 1)}{n^s}. \end{aligned}$$

730 Due to the conflict in Riemann's notation and the space-time definition
 731 of the variables, I define the dummy index, σ . The integrals in **Eq 43**) provide
 732 numerical relations between n and s , as well as n and s' ; and so, when we think
 733 of an inquisition like n^s, s^n , where n is a \mathbb{R} defined variable, which is a
 734 multivalued problem, because we choose the value for n , even if s is a variable.

735 $\prod(s' - 1), \prod(s - 1)$ are functions which do nothing more than
 736 compactify this notation. One could perform the integral of course with
 737 Integration By Parts or Taylor's theorem. One might do so by Taylor expanding
 738 all three functions, namely $e^{-n\sigma}, \sigma^{s-1}$, and $\sigma^{s'-1}$ and determine what
 739 $\prod(s' - 1), \prod(s - 1)$ behave like. Clearly $\prod(s - 1)$ is in proportion to n^s .
 740 Because of the explicit relation to the prime numbers the sum over $n^s, n^{s'}$ has **Eq**
 741 **41**), and the definition of n^s through the definition in **Eq 43**), we can work towards
 742 creating a continuous analysis of the prime numbers, who with respect to us, and
 743 every observer, understand this arbitrary definition as 2, 3, 5, 7...Riemann then
 744 uses these fact by adventuring us to explore some properties of this function which
 745 defines such a convergence: "The many-valued function $(-\sigma)^{s'-1} = e^{(s'-1)\ln(-\sigma)}$
 746 is \mathbb{R} when $\sigma < 0$." However, when x is positive, we must extend the analysis, as
 747 $f(x)^{k(x)} = (-f(x)^{k(x)} e^{-i\pi k(x)})$ shows this peculiarity of exponential functions.
 748 We will obviously also consider $(-\sigma)^{s-1} = e^{(s-1)\ln(-\sigma)}$. Next, Riemann works to
 749 understand $Z(s')$. We will simultaneously create an unprimed analysis by
 750 understanding $Z(s)$.

751 The operator Riemann used to convert $Z(s)$ into $\zeta(s)$ can be from **Eq**
 752 **43**) as it can be written in the form:

$$\hat{\zeta} \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(n\sigma)} \sigma^{s-1} d\sigma = \frac{\Pi(s-1)}{n^s} \right) \rightarrow \Pi(s-1)\zeta(s) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1} dx}{e^x - 1} \quad \text{Eq 44)}$$

753 And the equivalent definition of the primed zeta function can be found
754 from the symmetric operation:

$$\hat{\zeta}' \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(n\sigma)} \sigma^{s'-1} d\sigma = \frac{\Pi(s'-1)}{n^{s'}} \right) \rightarrow \Pi(s'-1)\zeta(s') = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s'-1} dx}{e^x - 1} \quad \text{Eq 45)}$$

755 As a side note in general the set of possible zeta functions that can be
756 formed can be constructed by generalizing the summand and integrand to
757 something like:

$$\hat{\zeta} \left(\int_0^{\infty} g(n, \sigma) h(s, \sigma)^{k(s, \sigma)-1} d\sigma = f(n, s) \Pi(s-1) \right) \rightarrow \Pi(s-1)\zeta_f(s) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{l(x, s)^{k(s)-1} dx}{m(x)}. \quad \text{Eq 46)}$$

758 Then if we generalize the zeta operator, the space of zeta functions can
759 be constructed.

760 I combined here a few equations on the following line, so to show more
761 generally, what $Z(s')$ is defined as. For this reason and the fact that the operator
762 is symmetric there is no need to consider the primed equations but they are always
763 implied. It is two analyses at once, so, the easiest way to think about this is by
764 having two equal signs, without coloring the notation, so to distinguish
765 dimensionality. I reserve coloring the notation for CGR. It isn't necessary here.

$$i(e^{-\pi s i} - e^{\pi s i}) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sigma^{s'-1} d\sigma}{e^{\sigma} - 1} = 2 \sin(\pi s') \Pi(s'-1)\zeta(s') \quad \text{Eq 47)}$$

$$i(e^{-\pi s i} - e^{\pi s i}) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sigma^{s-1} d\sigma}{e^{\sigma} - 1} = 2 \sin(\pi s) \Pi(s-1)\zeta(s)$$

766 Just as all of the equations up until this point have all been symmetric, in
767 that, when we create some imaginary energy, there is a balancing imaginary
768 energy.

769 We now have a definition of $\zeta(s') \forall \mathbb{C}$ numbers s' .

770 Relations between $\zeta(s')$ and $\zeta(s'-1)$ deduce that the expression

771 $\Pi\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right) \pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}} \zeta(s')$ is the same when $s' = 1 - s'$.

772 This relation, actually has the symmetry for the zeta function occur at s'
773 $= \frac{1}{2}$. This is why if we set $t = 0$, we must have $x = \frac{1}{2}$. For the necessary condition
774 of symmetry for the zeros. Riemann next gears towards relating $\zeta(s')$ to $\xi(ct')$, a
775 function which is defined at this point of symmetry with respect to $\zeta(s')$. The
776 reason for this is that $\xi(ct')$ is created for the purpose Riemann wrote this paper,
777 to find a counting function of the Prime numbers up to a number T . Each time
778 new variables are introduced, we seek to eradicate our ignorance by determining
779 an expression of the new variable in terms of things which have been previously
780 defined. With the definitions Riemann provides, we have a definition of $\pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}}$ in
781 terms of variables which we know, as will all of the variables thus far:

$$\frac{1}{n^{s'}} \Pi\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right) \pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx, \quad \text{Eq 48)}$$

782 From which, **Eq 48)**

$$\prod\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right)\pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}}\zeta(s') = \frac{1}{s'(s'-1)} + \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx. \quad \text{Eq 49)}$$

783 *Aside:*

784 Before we continue on, let us summarize the prior, so that we have an affine
785 relationship between all of the functions and variables within the section thus far:

$$\frac{1}{n^{s'}} \equiv \frac{1}{\left(\prod\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right)\pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}}\right)} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx, \quad \text{Eq 50)}$$

786

$$\pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{\zeta(s')\prod\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right)}\right) \left(\frac{1}{s'(s'-1)} + \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx\right). \quad \text{Eq 51)}$$

787 So, we have a definition of The Zeta function through the insertion of
788 these definitions introduced thus far.

$$\prod_{\text{Prime \#s}}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1-\frac{1}{p^s}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}} \quad \text{Eq 52)}$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\prod\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right)\left(\frac{1}{\zeta(s')\prod\left(\frac{s'}{2}-1\right)}\right)\left(\frac{1}{s'(s'-1)} + \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx\right)\right)} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{\frac{s'}{2}-1} dx$$

789 *End Aside.*

790 Riemann continues: at $x' = \frac{1}{2}$, we may define the new function, $\xi(ct')$,
791 which is not a function of x' , and we will have the following interesting results.
792 Those results appear after this he writes this statement.

793 Riemann then defines the new function, $\xi(ct')$ with $\prod\left(\frac{x'+ict'}{2}\right)(x'+ict' -$
794 $1)\pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}}\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + ict'\right) \equiv \xi(ct')$

795 And next why he chose such values for $x' + ict'$:

$$\xi(ct')|_{x+ict=\frac{1}{2}+ict'} = \frac{1}{2} - (c^2t'^2 + \frac{1}{4}) \int_1^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\pi x} x^{-\frac{3}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{ct'}{2} \ln(x)\right) dx. \quad \text{Eq 53)}$$

796 He explains that this functions is finite $\forall t'$, and that the zeros of ξ must be between
797 $-\frac{1}{2} < \Re((ct')) < \frac{1}{2}$. This forces true the following:

798 The number of times (roots) n , $\xi(ct'_n) = 0$ occurs is $\approx \frac{T}{2\pi} \ln\left(\frac{T}{2\pi}\right) - \frac{T}{2\pi}$, that

799 because $\int_{0-\frac{1}{2}i}^{T+\frac{1}{2}i} d\ln(\xi(ct')) = i\left(T\ln\left(\frac{T}{2\pi}\right) - T\right)$ (taking the integral in the positive

800 sense); Notice that $\int_{0-\frac{1}{2}i}^{T+\frac{1}{2}i} d\ln(\xi(ct')) = 2\pi ni$.

801 Letting ct'_n be the roots of $\xi(ct')$, we can express $\xi(ct')$ in the following way as
 802 per Riemann's definitions.

$$\ln(\xi(ct')) = \sum_1^{\infty} \ln\left(1 - \frac{c^2 t'^2}{c^2 t_n'^2}\right) + \ln(\xi(0)). \quad \text{Eq 54)}$$

803

804

805 § 3.4)

806 **CGR and The Riemann Hypothesis**

807 The statement of Riemann's Hypothesis can be written in, many ways
 808 because of the intricate connection between the many discussed functions. In
 809 forcing $t' = it$, we have

$$810 \left(\mathbb{I}\left(\lim_{t' \rightarrow t'_n} ct'\right)\right) = \xi\left(\mathbb{R}\left(\lim_{t \rightarrow t_n} ct\right)\right).$$

811 Because $x' = x = 1/2$,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{1}{2} && \text{Eq 55)} \\ t &= a + ib \\ x' &= \frac{1}{2} \\ t' &= -b + ia. \end{aligned}$$

812 Testing to see whether the Zeta Energy follows the Riemann-Cauchy
 813 Equations with both it, and t , I find a sign difference where there should not exist
 814 one. It is however per our selection that these two functions will intersect at the
 815 zeros. It is clear that the sinusoidal nature of the solutions to these wave equations
 816 prevents any places not zero, from having this equation be true.

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial t^2} = 0 = \frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial t'^2} \quad \text{Eq 56)}$$

817 Here, though, the x derivatives will zero:

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{\partial^2 E_T}{\partial t'^2} \quad \text{Eq 57)}$$

818 Because these equations are concerning the same problem, $\xi(ct') +$
 819 $\xi(ct) = 0$ is simultaneously true as the intersection of
 820 $\prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1-\frac{1}{p^s}}$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}}$. Thus, creating an Energy function which is true
 821 only at the zeros, the places of certain intersection

$$E_T = \prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1-\frac{1}{p^s}} - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}} - \xi(ct') + \xi(ct), \quad \text{Eq 58)}$$

822 So that the zero equation becomes:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1-\frac{1}{p^s}}}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}}}{\partial t'^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct')}{\partial t'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 59)}$$

823 If we take $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_n}$ on this last equation we will have an explicit equation for t_n .

824 Such makes necessary $\frac{\partial a}{\partial t} = 1, \frac{\partial b}{\partial t} = i, \frac{\partial a}{\partial t'} = i, \frac{\partial b}{\partial t'} = -1$.

825 We arrive to the final zero equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}}}{\partial a^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}}}{\partial b^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}}}{\partial b^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{s'}}}{\partial a^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct')}{\partial b^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct')}{\partial a^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct)}{\partial a^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ct)}{\partial b^2} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 60)}$$

826 With the selection of $it = t'$, the cases become simpler.

827 Possible values for b : Riemann Ruled out $|b| < 1/2$

828 Case One: $-1/2 < b < 1/2$

829 $\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} - ict\right) = \infty \forall -1/2 < b < 1/2$, but $\xi(ct)$ had been
830 \equiv finite and bounded,

831 $\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + ci(ib + a)\right)$ is sinusoidal in b , and thus bounded with respect to b .

832 so b cannot be any positive or negative value

833 Case Two: $b = 0$

834 We are considering thus,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \prod_{Prime \#s}^{pn=\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^{\frac{1}{2}+ia}}}}{\partial a^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{\frac{1}{2}+ia}}}{\partial a^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(cia)}{\partial a^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(ca)}{\partial a^2} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 61)}$$

835 This Case can produce zeros. b can be zero, and because the zeros are symmetric,
836 b is zero.

837 $\xi(\mathbb{R}(ct')) + \xi(\mathbb{C}(ct'))$ can only be true at the intersection these surfaces

838 Because at $x = \frac{1}{2}$ is the only place which has the Real and Imaginary
839 surfaces can intersect, is with $x' = \frac{1}{2}$ is the only place which will have the
840 necessary condition, $\mathbb{R}(ct') = \mathbb{C}(ct)$. However, within the problem we defined,
841 because it was generally defined, and symmetrically, and that the zeros are real
842 with respect to x , the converse must be true, and so, an inverse equation, which
843 has a replacement of the variables shows that one is required to have, with respect
844 to t' , Real zeros.

845 Equations of Interest and their Properties

846 The function

$$\xi(ct')|_{\frac{1}{2}+ict'} = \frac{1}{2} - (c^2 t'^2 + \frac{1}{4}) \int_1^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi x} x^{-\frac{3}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{ct'}{2} \ln(x)\right) \quad \text{Eq 62)}$$

847 has n roots which are located at ct'_n , because $\xi(ct')$ can be expressed as a product

$$\xi(ct') = e^{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \ln(1 - \frac{c^2 t'^2}{c^2 t_n'^2}) + \ln(\xi(0))} \quad \text{Eq 63}$$

848

$$\xi(ct') = \xi(0) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{c^2 t'^2}{c^2 t_n'^2}\right). \quad \text{Eq 64}$$

849 When the variable $ct' = ct'_n$, we have found a root of $\xi(ct')$.

$$\prod \left(\frac{x' + ict'}{2}\right) (x' + ict' - 1) \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \zeta(x' + ict') \equiv \xi(ct') \quad \text{Eq 65}$$

850 From this, we know the relation between $\zeta(x' + ict')$ and the zeros, ct'_n of $\xi(ct')$.

851 Combining **Eq 64**, and the definition of $\xi(ct')$ **Eq 65**, I find:

$$\prod \left(\frac{x' + ict'}{2}\right) (x' + ict' - 1) \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \zeta(x' + ict') = \xi(0) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{c^2 t'^2}{c^2 t_n'^2}\right). \quad \text{Eq 66}$$

852 We see that, the claim, that only at $x' = \frac{1}{2}$ will $\xi(ct')$ be factorable in this

853 manner. If we thus find why $x' = \frac{1}{2}$, why this particular value of x' is chosen, we

854 can work towards understanding better, the nature of this multivalued problem.

855 With $t' \in \mathbb{C}$, we must consider Complex roots. However, it is also with $t' \in \mathbb{C}$ that

856 we have to consider multiple components to x' , so to maintain continuity of $\xi(ct')$.

857 With $t \equiv a' + ib'$, and $t'_n \equiv a'_n + ib'_n$, we have an equation for the roots.

$$\xi(ct') = \xi(0) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{(a' + ib)^2}{(a'_n + ib'_n)^2}\right); \quad \text{Eq 67}$$

858

$$\xi(ct') = \xi(0) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{((a'^2 - b'^2) + 2ib)(a'_n - ib'_n)}{(a_n'^4 - 2b_n'^2(a_n'^2 + 2) + b_n'^4)}\right). \quad \text{Eq 68}$$

859 Working to express the roots as a general polynomial

$$\xi(ct') = \xi(0) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{((a'^2))(a'_n - ib'_n)}{(a_n'^4 - 2b_n'^2(a_n'^2 + 2) + b_n'^4)}\right), \quad \text{Eq 69}$$

860 so, with defining $A(a'_n, b'_n)$, in placement of the coefficients of the Taylor

861 expansion of ξ provides us with

$$\xi(ct') = \xi(0) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{A(a'_n, b'_n)(ct' - k)^n \left(d^n \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{((a(k)^2))(a'_n - ib'_n)}{(a_n'^4 - 2b_n'^2(a_n'^2 + 2) + b_n'^4)}\right) \right)}{n!} \quad \text{Eq 70}$$

862 It was my intention to speed through this, so that we can, as we think

863 about these functions in the Imaginary Realm, have the working definitions of the

864 functions involved with this hypothesis. Because Riemann created these functions

865 to exhibit the end result he wanted. To him, it was simply deduction:

866 At this particular x' value, we have $\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + ict'\right) = \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} - ict'\right)$ for $t' \in \mathbb{C}$, and $-\frac{1}{2c}$
 867 $< \Re((ct')) < \frac{1}{2c}$. This implies that the Real zeros of $\xi(ca')$ have the following
 868 domain:

$$\zeta(\pm ica') < \xi(ca') < \zeta\left(\pm ica' + \frac{1}{4}\right). \quad \text{Eq 71)}$$

869 And repressing this gives us an equality which bounds a' , which has been created
 870 to sustain the experiment.

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{\pm ica'}} < \frac{1}{2} - \left(c^2 t'^2 + \frac{1}{4}\right) \int_1^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi x} x^{-\frac{3}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{ca'}{2} \ln(x)\right) < \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt[4]{nn^{\pm ica'}}} \quad \text{Eq 72)}$$

871 Using $f(x)^{k(x)} = (-f(x)^{k(x)} e^{-i\pi k(x)})$, we can express Z as a surface:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x'} \cos(ct' \ln(n)) - i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x'} \sin(ct' \ln(n)) + \prod_{\text{Prime \#s}} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^s}} = 0 \\ & -e^{-i\pi x'} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-n)^{-x'} \cos(ct' \ln(n)) - ie^{-i\pi x'} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-n)^{-x'} \sin(ct' \ln(n)) + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 73)}$$

872 *Additional*

873 It is this same property which is responsible for the Euler relation $e^{i\pi} = -1$.
 874 From symmetry it must be true that:

$$\frac{\left(i(e^{-\pi si} - e^{\pi si}) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1} dx}{e^x - 1} + i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(-x)^{s-1} dx}{e^x - 1}\right)}{\sin(\pi s) \prod(s-1)} = \frac{e^{\wedge} (\sum_1^{\infty} \ln(1 - \frac{c^2 t'^2}{c^2 t_n^2}) + \ln(\xi(0)))}{\prod\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) (s-1) \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}} \quad \text{Eq 74)}$$

875 The division of $\sin((\pi s))$ in every term provides for a respective minimum value
 876 for every term.

877 **§ 3.5)**

878 **Riemann's Conjecture**

879 The Riemann Zeta function, $Z(s) = Z(x + iy) = \sum_n^{\infty} n^{-s}$, as defined in
 880 B. Riemann's 1859 manuscript is the convergence of the Euler Product and the
 881 sum over n^{-s} after Analytic Continuation is performed. The convergence of these
 882 two expressions thus require the analysis of two functions, $\zeta(s) = \zeta(x + iy)$ and
 883 $\zeta(s') = \zeta(x' + iy') = \zeta(x - y)$ due to the symmetry of the zeros, $\zeta(a + ib) =$
 884 $\zeta(a - ib)$ [70]. We select arbitrarily $x' = x$, so in doing, to find places which
 885 will still hold true the definition of symmetry, which can be obtained by verifying
 886 the primed Riemann-Cauchy equations yield the same result with respect to the
 887 unprimed equations for the arbitrary selection of $x' = x$, and $y' = iy$. In other
 888 words, to prove that the Riemann-Cauchy equations, when written, with $\Re(y) =$
 889 $\Re(y')$, $\Re(y) = -\Re(y')$, is true for both the primed and unprimed co-ordinates, is
 890 to prove the desired property of symmetry with respect to the definitions of y' and
 891 y . The property of invariance is what shows the symmetry exists. To see that this
 892 condition is met see *Lemma 1.0*. We are this arises from the definition of the Zeta
 893 function, where symmetry is imposed at $s = 1 - s$, or $s = \frac{1}{2}$. In order to find
 894 equations which are true at the zeros, we must only maintain this symmetry and
 895 continuity.

896 In Leonhard Euler's *Introductio* [72], Euler provides us with the relation
 897 between Complex exponentials [73] and the Sine and Cosine functions. After first
 898 determining the polynomial representation of $\text{Sin}(x)$ and $\text{Cos}(x)$, he understood
 899 a pattern between the three series relations. In proving this approximation with
 900 nothing more than Algebra, which was evidently the task of *Introductio*, Euler
 901 manipulated "infinite numbers," where for example, $\theta = \frac{x}{n}$ we apply $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \theta$, to
 902 understand theta as* zero. In such a limit, $e^{n\theta}, \text{Sin}(n\theta), \text{Cos}(n\theta)$ the series
 903 representation reduces to,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cos}(x) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{ix}{n}\right)^n + \left(1 - \frac{ix}{n}\right)^n \right)}{2}, & \text{Eq 75)} \\ \text{Sin}(x) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{ix}{n}\right)^n - \left(1 - \frac{ix}{n}\right)^n \right)}{2i}. \end{aligned}$$

904 In modern times, these limits are well defined as e^{ix}, e^{-ix} .

905 In replacing cosine and sine terms in for $Z(s), Z(s')$, supposing we define
 906 a symmetric function, one which obeys the Riemann-Cauchy equations with
 907 respect to the zeros of these functions we find an expression which will show us
 908 how in this limit, after the zeta function has been expanded to its Complex form.

$$\begin{aligned} Z(s) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k + \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2} & \text{Eq 76)} \\ &+ \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k - \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2i}. \end{aligned}$$

909 This is a way to imagine a limit for the Quantadimension. I am going to
 910 omit the writing of the second set of functions. They are implied to exist.
 911 Manipulating **Eq 76)** will show us this.

$$Z(s) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^T \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right) \quad \text{Eq 79)}$$

912 This transformation is continuous. There exist other types of zeta
 913 functions like the Dirichlet series, the L-Functions [74] and Mellin
 914 Transformations [75], which are strongly related to the differential equation
 915 methodology in Fourier and Laplace Transformations [76]. It immediately
 916 follows that $1^{-s} + 2^{-s} \dots$ can be written as a polynomial [77] whose coefficients
 917 are determined by the roots [78]. The roots thus are Unique, in the sense, that if a
 918 function is defined in a way which perhaps an Algebraic operation [79], or
 919 transformed by the application of any mathematical theorem [80] and hence
 920 reduction of the apparatus which is defined symmetrically through the respective
 921 cyclic nature the $(x - b, ia), (x - a, ib)$ systems.

Eq 78)

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^T \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k + \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2} \\ &+ \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k - \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2i}. \end{aligned}$$

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It is simultaneously true that the primed zeros are at the same places as the unprimed zeros :

Eq 79)

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^T \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right) \\ &- \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k'_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^T \frac{(-1)^{k'_T} (s' - s'_j)^{k'_T} \ln^{k'_T}(s'_j)}{k'_j! n^T} \right) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k + \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2} \\ &+ \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k - \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2i} \\ &- \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k + \left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2} \\ &- \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} i \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \frac{\left(\left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k - \left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k \right)}{2i}, \end{aligned}$$

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It is from this equation that we obtain the fullest amount of information we can exploit thus far. It is clear that if we wish to ϵy to \mathbb{C} , we must too $\epsilon y'$ to \mathbb{C} the exact same way. The analysis thus extends to thinking about more functions, to even include these Complex valued [81] roots $\left(\frac{1}{2}, y_n = a + ib\right)$, $\left(\frac{1}{2}, y'_n = -b + ia\right)$. Riemann introduced functions of the Complex variable y [82], $\xi(y)$ so I introduce into the analysis, a symmetric function $\xi(y')$ whose introduction is required through symmetry of the introduction of new variables is:

$$\prod \left(\frac{x' + iy}{2} \right) (x + iy - 1) \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + iy \right) \equiv \xi(y), \quad \text{and Eq 80)$$

$$\prod \left(\frac{x' + iy'}{2} \right) (x' + iy' - 1) \pi^{-\frac{s'}{2}} \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + iy' \right) \equiv \xi(y')$$

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G. H. Hardy discovered that there exists infinitely many zeros at the critical strip [83], and so, $\zeta(s), \zeta(s')$ intersect infinitely many times at the critical strip. The Complex space-time vectors for this problem have co-ordinates: $s = \langle x + a, ib \rangle, s' = \langle x - b, ia \rangle$. As per Riemann the zeros of $\xi(y)$ can be written as a product, due to Eq 63)

$$\ln(\xi(y)) = \sum_1^{\infty} \ln\left(1 - \frac{y^2}{y_n^2}\right) + \ln(\xi(0)), \quad \text{Eq 81)}$$

936 or

$$\xi(y) = \xi(0) \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{y_n^2}\right), \quad \text{Eq 82)}$$

937 Again, here, the primed equations are implied to exist.

938 And we now have an equation which is symmetric and only true at the
 939 intersection of these surfaces, the possible cases for y_n are: limited because
 940 Riemann had proven $-\frac{i}{2} < (y_n) < \frac{i}{2}$.¹¹ and we know already

$$941 \quad 0 < \Re(y_n) < \infty.$$

942 It is because $s' = s = \frac{1}{2}$ that $x' = x = \frac{1}{2}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \cdots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^{T=\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right)}{\partial x^2} \\ & + \frac{\partial^2 \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \left(1 + \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(0) \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{y_n^2}\right)}{\partial y^2} = 0 \\ & = \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k_0=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} \cdots \sum_{k_T=0}^{\infty} \prod_{j=0}^{T=\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k_T} (s - s_j)^{k_T} \ln^{k_T}(s_j)}{k_j! n^T} \right)}{\partial x^2} \\ & - \frac{\partial^2 \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n^{-x} \left(1 - \frac{iy \ln(n)}{k}\right)^k}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(0) \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{y^2}{y_n^2}\right)}{\partial y^2} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 83)}$$

943 So we are only concerned with places of symmetry. The Riemann zeros
 944 occur at the critical strip with $x = x' = \frac{1}{2}$, and because y is simultaneously
 945 approaching a zero, and zeros occur most definitely between $-\frac{1}{2} < \Im(y) < \frac{1}{2}$
 946 simultaneously at $x' = \frac{1}{2} = x$, we know for certain that then all viable places this
 947 can occur, has $\Im(y_n) = 0$.

948 Further,

949 The insertion of $|\Im(y_n)| < \frac{1}{2}$ breaks the symmetry of the problem, which,
 950 given the parameterization of the translation, cannot occur.

951 If $\Im(y_n) > 0$ we see that because $s = 1/2 + i\Re(y_n) - \Im(y_n)$, and $s' =$
 952 $1/2 - i\Re(y'_n) + \Im(y'_n)$, where zeros require symmetry, and hence $s = s'$, we
 953 find that $i(\Re(y_n) + \Re(-y_n)) = \Im(y_n) + \Im(-y_n)$ which shows us that

$$954 \quad \Re(y_n) + \Re(-y_n) = 0, \text{ which is by definition, true, and } \Im(y_n) + \Im(-y_n) =$$

$$955 \quad 0.$$

956 Thus, because $(y_n) = -(-y_n)$, and, when we have $(y_n) > 0$, symmetry is broken
 957 because of the opposite nature of the primed system and unprimed system.

958 We thus have proven Riemann's Hypothesis because in order to translate
 959 the variables to CGR's notation, a symmetric theory, one is required to drop the
 960 Imaginary component for the zeros of the functions. This is indication that b

961 cannot be a $\pm\mathbb{R}$ number because it would make a discontinuity in CGR to do so.
 962 It is because of the fact that the zeros of the Zeta function are symmetric that a
 963 continuous logical translation into the notation of CGR would have the conditions
 964 of symmetry to be met. The verification of this is the respective Analyticity [86]
 965 that has been verified in several places and by several means extensively
 966 throughout this book.

967 *Lemma 1.0 Riemann-Cauchy Conditions are Met:*

968 Because we know that the places where these functions are defined are
 969 at least true for the zeros, we have

$$\zeta(s) + \zeta(s') + i\xi(y) + i\xi(y') = 0 \quad \text{Eq 84}$$

970 The functions $E(\zeta(s), i\xi(y))$ and $E(\zeta(s'), i\xi(y'))$, must follow a modification to
 971 the Riemann-Cauchy conditions,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \zeta(s)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \zeta(s')}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi(y)}{\partial y^2} = \frac{d^2 E_t}{dt^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \zeta(s')}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \zeta(s')}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \xi(-y)}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 85}$$

972 § 5

973 **5-D Surfaces**

974 The coming sections are the numbered steps for turning a purely theoretical
 975 and mathematical problem [87] into a physics problem [88] which is why I have
 976 designed sections **1.0** → **4**) so that if one inserts "Complex" anywhere one sees
 977 "zeta," one can generalize. To consider a zeta function as a function of s , and that
 978 the constituent components which comprise s are x and iy , is to make that zeta
 979 function as a function of x and iy . We do not need to use s ; it is a strictly \mathbb{R} defined
 980 parameter, as x and y , so we can immediately generalize by realizing that when y
 981 is equal to zero, we see the function as only a function of x , a \mathbb{R} variable.

982 The goal is to be able to view The Zeta function as a creature who is trapped
 983 in the \mathbb{R} domain, and separately a creature who can see \mathbb{C} numbers, so that we can
 984 view zeta functions from these two unique perspectives; a "Complex creature,"
 985 and a "Real creature." To continuously transport the number $x + iy$ to the new
 986 number $U + iV$ is to perform an operation on the number. In modern terms,
 987 $\zeta(x + iy) = U(x, y) + iV(x, y)$. To visualize this, one may look at the \mathbb{R} surface
 988 U , and \mathbb{I} surface V , as a function of x and y . When locating zeros of zeta functions,
 989 this visualization helps because we are interested in the places where the \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{I}
 990 surface (which are with respect to x and y) intersect.

991 **1.0) On the Equating of Vector and Scalar Interpretations, and how to**
 992 **Imagine a 5-D Function:**

993 With respect to the original axes, (x, iy) , functions of x summed to iy are co-
 994 ordinate transformations [89] to the new bases (U, iV) . This concept is the
 995 fundamental concept of Relativity in disguise: it is the same surface, just looked
 996 at another way. Just as the variables are related in Relativity, one might consider
 997 that the coordinates are parameterized by a single variable, so that Complex
 998 valued functions can have Continuity forced upon them. Riemann suggested a
 999 very neat way to think of this: imagine the number $x + iy$, and continuously
 1000 transport it to the new number $U + iV$, and those are the only type of surfaces
 1001 $(U(x, y), V(x, y))$ which make sense.

1002 I am implying here for you to imagine the same process for every point on a
 1003 surface, or even a Manifold [90] that is representative of an Energy function,
 1004 which can be imagined in 5 dimensions (in the example of Energy functions) as a
 1005 surface which is colored continuously by the knowledge of color to be
 1006 representative of a frequency of an Electromagnetic Wave, which also lies on a
 1007 continuous scale (the Electromagnetic Spectrum), then having the surface itself

1008 move in time with respect to the x, y, z co-ordinates where we imagined the
1009 surface to be located, and having the color of the surface simultaneously change
1010 in time, where the color vector (whose frequency is omega) can be visualized as
1011 the Energy (direction) component in Relativity, to make
1012 $(\omega(x, y, z, t), ict, x(t), y(t), z(t))$ with respect to the places the 3-vectors
1013 appear on an infinitesimal tangent plane to the surface, but then having the vectors
1014 be colored continuously by the EM spectrum, so that the directional change in
1015 time can be determined by the differential in color..

1016 Relativity suggests that there are infinitely many viable ways to place the co-
1017 ordinates in an analysis. Consider an ant walking along the surface of a table.
1018 Depending on whether you are on the Northside of the table, or West, you may
1019 find different functions describing the path the ant traverses –even though you
1020 define the co-ordinate system in the same way (hopefully a right-handed Cartesian
1021 system for ease). It is necessary to understand that the table, if you were standing
1022 in the West with respect to a map placed upon the table, is the same table and ant
1023 even if you decided to walk to be Northside of the table to observe the happening.
1024 It is the same happening, but viewed from two different places. The results must
1025 agree independent of how you describe the happening.

1026 If one supposes that all of the sensible functions we analyze in mathematics
1027 are to behave smoothly, as do all functions which follow the continuous laws of
1028 nature, one might assert that all of the variables we analyze are functions which
1029 are connected in some way such that they are parameterized by a single variable.
1030 I'll use (t) because time is traditionally this variable in physics considerations. This
1031 parameterization will allow for us to understand the individually separate numbers
1032 as a collective and supply one with an intuitive physical image in one's mind such
1033 to view The Zeta function as an Energy function. If we parameterize the variables,
1034 we can make better sense of the happenings. If we let x , and iy be functions of t ,
1035 so that the zeta function is a function of strictly t , the insertion of the derivative of
1036 x with respect to t as one, and the derivative of y with respect to t as i , we can
1037 analyze continuously The Zeta function by letting all of its composing variables
1038 to be connected by the parameter t . This is an implication that a zeta function can
1039 be visualized by looking individually at the components of The Zeta function, and
1040 how they affect the outcome, then "sewing together" the individual pieces. This
1041 is written more compactly as $x, y \rightarrow x(t), y(t) \mid \frac{dx}{dt} = 1, \frac{dy}{dt} = i$.

1042 Energy functions are functions of the underlying co-ordinates which describe
1043 an event which is localized at those co-ordinates. Energy cannot be discontinuous,
1044 because then, the Conservation of Energy is broken. Further, supposing the
1045 conception that objects reside in space-time, the connected continuum, we require
1046 continuity of the underlying co-ordinates simply because if the co-ordinates
1047 themselves are discontinuous in time, our logical analysis becomes illogical, and
1048 is no longer connected. The space-time media is continuous by definition. It is the
1049 fabric of the universe, and the universe is always comprehensible, even when we
1050 are ignorant as to why.

1051 § 5.2)

1052 Definition of 2-D Complex Space-time Vectors

1053 Here, it is useful to consider the thoughts of Gauss to extend the number plane
1054 to naturally include for one dimensional considerations, the perpendicularity of
1055 another scaled number line, so that the number axes read: x , and (in our case) the
1056 axis perpendicular to x is act , for a constant, $a = i$. Riemann took the concept
1057 further, so that any function which we are interested are the ones which can be
1058 described continuously in this plane which describes all naturally occurring

1059 numbers in physics. 2) will discuss these continuity conditions for "Analytic
 1060 Functions." I have found that this concept in the formulation of 2-D Relativity is
 1061 useful. These phasors are similar to vectors [92]. Consider the equation

1062 *Definition:*

$$s'(x', t') = s'(x + ict) = x'(x, t) + ict'(x, t) \quad \text{Eq 86}$$

1063 but think about it differently: consider not two scalar valued independent
 1064 parameters, but instead a two vector with \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{I} component,

1065 $\vec{s} = \begin{pmatrix} ict \\ x \end{pmatrix}$, (which we may well have written as $\vec{s} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ ict \end{pmatrix}$) so that we
 1066 continuously transport this 2-vector to the space-time point describing the primed
 1067 co-ordinates,

$$s'(\vec{s}) = \overline{s'(x', t')} = \begin{pmatrix} x'(x, t) \\ ict'(x, t) \end{pmatrix}. \quad \text{Eq 87}$$

1068 Cartesian vectors [93] (orthogonal number axes) will follow the flat space-time
 1069 magnitude rule [94] (Pythagorean Theorem [95]), the same interval rule, $ds^2 =$
 1070 ds'^2 .

1071 To consider an infinitesimal change, we recognize that x and t are functions
 1072 of the primed co-ordinates, so that the infinitesimal change in The Interval [96] is

$$\overline{ds} = \begin{pmatrix} dx \\ ictdt \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial x'} dx' + \frac{\partial x}{\partial t'} dt' \\ ic \frac{\partial t}{\partial x'} dx' + ic \frac{\partial t}{\partial t'} dt' \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 88}$$

1073 From here, one can see why $ds^2 = ds'^2$ is not true in co-ordinates which are not
 1074 permanently orthogonal [97] to one another.

1075 **§ 5.3), Proof The Continuity Condition for Complex-Physical Systems By**
 1076 **Verification with Harmonic, Second Order Riemann-Cauchy Equations:**
 1077 **Riemann Zero Condition**

1078 Parameterization of Translated Variables

1079 *Definition:*

$$\zeta(x + iy) \equiv U(x, y) + iV(x, y); \quad \text{Eq 89}$$

1080 A parameterization of (x, y) by t forces all of the variables to be.

1081 *Proof:*

$$1082 \quad U(x, y), V(x, y) \rightarrow U(t), V(t); \text{ and } \zeta \rightarrow \zeta(t).$$

1083 It's much like viewing the zeta function as being an Energy function. With this
 1084 being the case, The Zeta function will follow the Extremal Energy Condition of
 1085 Physics [98]:

1086 *Proof of this minimization idea after parametrization [99]:*

$$\frac{d\zeta}{dt} = 0. \quad \text{Eq 90}$$

1087 Once expanded with The Chain Rule, and the above insertions, I find

$$0 = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right); \quad \text{Eq 91}$$

1088 further, zero is only achieved at the intersection of the real surface and the
 1089 imaginary surface, when $\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial V}{\partial y}$, and $\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial x}$. The Mathematicians will
 1090 better recognize these equations as the Riemann-Cauchy equations.

1091 The second partial derivatives will yield the "mysterious" wave-like co-
 1092 ordinates which appear in Quantum Mechanics. When one must consider
 1093 "imaginary" particles, particles with negative energies, one has to view life in
 1094 these naturally wave-like mathematical coordinates, $\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2}$;
 1095 which can be expressed more compactly as $\frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt^2} = 0$;

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} = \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} = \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt^2} = 0. \quad \text{Eq 92)}$$

1096 When $y = ct$, one will have something which looks like the one
 1097 dimensional Wave Equation [100] from Electrodynamics; namely, $\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} -$
 1098 $\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2}$. This suggests that the viewing of the problem by
 1099 Riemann can be understood in modern terms with the change of the y variables
 1100 to be the temporal co-ordinate for the arc-length, as suggested for Hermann
 1101 Minkowski's four-vector describing such a length.

1102 Newton's equations of motion can be readily derived by the Euler-
 1103 Lagrange interpretation of Classical Mechanics. In fact, most field modern field
 1104 theories define an action in terms of an integral which will be later minimized
 1105 by techniques like Hamilton's Variational Principle [101]. For example: the
 1106 Geodesic Equation [102] and Field Equations [103] of General Relativity can be
 1107 derived in this fashion; the Einstein-Hilbert action [104] is an integral which is
 1108 minimized with Hamilton's Principle. The area beneath the curve is minimized
 1109 to find the equations which must obey always the underlying law: Conservation
 1110 of Energy. Thus, defining an arbitrary function which is extremal always, is to
 1111 fit it to the Law of Conservation. This is good for us because Analytic functions
 1112 obey this already. For more information, see extremization of functions.

1113 It is necessary to see here that the "Quanta-Dimension" is one in the
 1114 same as our realm. The Quantum Realm of Physics must be a co-ordinate
 1115 transformation of our current perception. After all... particles compose us, even
 1116 if they are tough to see. Distant galaxies and nebulae can also be tough to see,
 1117 even though they're humongous if one were to actually approach these points in
 1118 the sky.

1119 If you arbitrarily define the energy of a particle to be negative, you can
 1120 achieve imaginary velocities. There is no need for us to truncate these terms, or
 1121 even radically alter our theory to account for them. They will follow the same
 1122 Laws of Physics that the "real" particle follows. This is essentially the concept
 1123 of anti-particles, \bar{l} particles.

1124 **CHANGE OF NOTATION:** I will stop using the variable y, and instead use
 1125 this parameterization by t. It will help for us to get an idea for how to see this
 1126 imaginary zeta function we have crafted, as an Energy function which follows
 1127 the laws of Physics.

1128 **5.4) Newtonian Implications of Equal and Opposite Forces, and the**
 1129 **Symmetric Structure of General Relativity: Amendment to Riemann Zero**
 1130 **Condition**

1131 Newton's Force Laws [105], Relativity, and the functioning postulates thereof,
 1132 ensure that in order to observe an event resulting from an interaction, we must
 1133 consider the cause of the event. These Force Vectors can be visualized also as the

1134 previously mentioned Vector Field: $\vec{E} \rightarrow \vec{E} \left(\begin{pmatrix} x'_0 \\ \vdots \\ x'_3 \end{pmatrix} \right) = E(\vec{s}'(x'_0,$

1135 $x'_1, x'_2, x'_3))$, which is acting on the co-ordinates of a space-time (as viewed by
 1136 x'). Because of the requirement that we must consider \mathbb{I} components to understand
 1137 subatomic particles (which can have Scalar valued Energy functions) with The
 1138 Relativistic 4-vector (same idea as **1.1**), but viewed in higher dimensions) we can
 1139 extend this concept to Vector Fields [106] (so that the Vector Field E has scalar
 1140 components determined from the co-ordinates which are allowing for E to exist),
 1141 where in the simplest case, The Electric Field takes the form of The Coulomb
 1142 Potential [107] which has an inverse square proportionality [108], of course
 1143 regarding the distance.

1144 This implies that the problem with **1**) and **2**) is that we haven't yet considered
 1145 how this interaction can occur; that is, we need another function to "balance" The
 1146 Zeta-Energy, so that everywhere, these two functions, when added together cancel
 1147 each other; this is, if we create an energy (which is our imagination thinking of
 1148 the zeta function as a representative energy function) some completely opposite
 1149 energy must simultaneously be guaranteed to exist such to maintain the truth of
 1150 The Conservation of Energy. Once we imagine viewing the zeta function as an
 1151 energy function, and we understand that there must be an equal balancing function
 1152 with such a thought, we can start to think about what it will look like from other
 1153 perspectives, like that of x' . It is clear the modification for the primes can be
 1154 encompassed with the usage of colors:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} &= \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} = \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt^2} = 0 = 0 & \text{Eq 93)} \\ &= \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y'^2} = \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt'^2} = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y'^2} \\ &= \frac{d^2 \zeta}{dt'^2} \end{aligned}$$

1155 The incompatibility of the integral and differential interpretation provided by
 1156 the Divergence Theorem [109] when finding the divergence of the inverse squared
 1157 separation distance between an Electrostatic charge [110], is rectified through the
 1158 Dirac Delta Function [111]. This same issue, in a more general sense exists in GR.
 1159 It is due to the spherical nature of the composing Electric Potentials that large
 1160 collections of particles have still this respective spherical symmetry.

1161 **§ 5.5) Equality of Quanta-Dimension's Time to Electrostatic-Dimension's**
 1162 **Time Through Analogy of Clock as Seen By Two Different Observers**

1163 On the Notion of Time with Respect to a Clock:

1164 In fact is it true that there are an infinite number of ways to think of the
 1165 placement of the co-ordinates on any object. In addition to locations one may
 1166 place the origin of the co-ordinates, there are infinitely many scale factors of the
 1167 numbers in the co-ordinate system which may be considered; for example, the
 1168 usage of units of feet versus meters to describe lengths on the planet Earth (both
 1169 are flat x, y, z systems, but they are scale factors of one another). The fundamental
 1170 result of Relativity is that the laws of physics will work the same –independent of
 1171 whether you are using the metric system, or some other measurement system.

1172 Consider now, a transparent clock situated at $x=0$ (with respect to the
 1173 clock), so that two observers; identical twin robots with cameras that have straight

1174 ahead, the positive x , and in the vertical, a positive y axis, both see the same thing
 1175 from two perspectives; situated at $a = x$, and $-a = x'$ (the distance with
 1176 respect to the clock [112] of the observers is a), of an x'_1 (clocks) axis, so that on
 1177 the side of x' , the clock moves clockwise, reading the numbers as 1, 2, 3 ... to 12,
 1178 where the arm of the clock only knows this procedure, the numbers to the clock
 1179 arm always go in this order, but to the unprimed x observer, the numbers, when
 1180 x wants to understand the clock (thinking of the arm's view of the numbers) lie
 1181 also at 1, 2, 3, ... 12, even though to the clocks view, the numbers must read to the
 1182 primed observer as $-1, -2, -3 \dots -12$ (due to the motion required to do that
 1183 action having a negative direction), In Physics, negatives denote directions of the
 1184 vector quantities \vec{x}' and \vec{x} , so with respect to the clock's axis, $x'_1 = \frac{x'-x}{2}$. This
 1185 shows that x'_1 can be an only real valued parameter, and still yet maintain functions
 1186 which are composed of Complex scalar valued functions. This previous statement
 1187 is only true if the respective velocity between x and x' is constant. Suppose that
 1188 the clock is infinitely small, for example, the size of an atom. Of course, this
 1189 presumes that one assumes velocities for the clock are which are non-linear. To
 1190 make this analysis easier, shrink the clock to be the size of an Atom, and let x ,
 1191 and x' be with respect to each other, with respect to a Quantum sized origin.

1192
 1193 **§ 5.6) The Respective Logical Contradiction Between the Classical and**
 1194 **Quantum Descriptions of Mechanics; Maxwell's Electromagnetic Wave**
 1195 **Theorem**

1196 The Contradiction of the Electromagnetic Wave Theorem, and Quantum
 1197 Mechanics, 1:

1198 The truncation of Imaginary solutions to the differential equations which
 1199 describe phenomena on the Electrostatic-Dimension is the primary issue which has
 1200 propagated into the Classical description of GR because of its similarity.

1201
 1202 Consider Maxwell's uncoupled equations as of Electrodynamics,

1203
$$\nabla^2 \vec{E} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} = \mu \vec{J}$$
 This equation reads as: the motion of some
 1204 charge(s), $\vec{J}(x, y, z, t)$, will create an electric field $\vec{E}(x, y, z, t)$ which follows the
 1205 above Helmholtz Equation [113], and similarly with the magnetic field equations.
 1206 The concept of Relativity is that without a charge present, there will be nothing to
 1207 create Electromagnetic Radiation. Electromagnetic waves are simply a wavelike
 1208 variation of an electric field which is created by a charge's acceleration. Without
 1209 a charge displacing itself relative to an observer, in time, there would be no such
 1210 equation because nothing interesting would be happening. What I am suggesting
 1211 here is that the concept of observing radiation without a charge to produce such is
 1212 not sensible; that is, it is a direct logical contradiction with the apparatus of GR to
 1213 set \vec{J} to zero, and somehow still observe radiation. To eliminate the contradiction
 1214 let us, instead of observing this equation absent of a charge, imagine such a charge
 1215 from the co-ordinates x, y, z, t , and take $\lim_{x,y,z \rightarrow x',y',z'} J(x, y, z, t)$, so that the
 1216 primed observer is effectively "standing on top" of the charge. In this sense,
 1217 $\vec{J}(x', y', z', t)$ will vanish, and we will be left with

1218
$$\nabla^2 \vec{E}(x', y', z', t') + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}(x', y', z', t')}{\partial t'^2} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 94}$$

1218 This equation is known to produce the general wave solution [114], with
 1219 a \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{I} part, where the \mathbb{I} part is generally truncated due to its uselessness, as it
 1220 is in circuit dynamics*. This logic, of viewing life as a particle, I think of as being
 1221 a "zoom" operation. In essence, one zooms in or out to view co-ordinates from a
 1222 more sensible location. This is what is done on the galactic scale, where giant
 1223 objects which are a coalescence of many infinitely tiny points, are viewed as being

1224 single points due to the distance that the respective forcing bodies are away from
1225 one another. With this in mind, Schrödinger's equation [115] which describes how
1226 to obtain the wave function, doesn't necessarily bend logic. It's like the wave
1227 function, $\psi(x, y, z, t)$, which is a function of the co-ordinates, is actually a scaling
1228 function to better see the infinitesimally small energy of a particle. If we let The
1229 Energy of a particle to obey Classical Mechanics, in the sense that The Energy is
1230 equivalent to half the mass of the particle multiplied by the square of the velocity,
1231 one may take the suggestion of de Broglie [116], that the particle has an oscillatory
1232 velocity in free space, so that both the energy and velocity of the particle can be
1233 written as constants, we will be able to receive the Schrodinger equation:

1234 _____
1235 *An example of this occurs in Fundamentals of Electric Circuits, Alexander [25].
1236

1237 § 5.7) The Theoretical Description of Anti-Particles for CGR

1238
1239 On the Electromagnetic Wave Theorem, and its Implications from Relativity into
1240 Quantum Mechanics, 2:

1241 The Heisenberg and the Schrodinger interpretation together give the full
1242 picture of Quantum Mechanics. Electrons, thought by Sir Isaac Newton and
1243 Democritus to be discrete corpuscles which by the postulates of CGR must have
1244 a space-time description, and hence determinable trajectories for the spatial and
1245 temporal co-ordinates that the particles is defined to be at. It is clear that the
1246 description of the co-ordinates of a "particle" or "corpuscle," if we so wish to
1247 ensure that CGR is consistent with the most accurate descriptions of nature, we
1248 must produce the wave like Intensity distribution patterns electrons exhibit in even
1249 a variant of the Two Slit Experiment where the electrons are fired singly this wave
1250 like Intensity pattern when the experiment is performed a sufficient amount of
1251 time.

1252 Any attempt to rectify GR, a theory which necessitates, for mathematical
1253 purposes, determinable trajectories in the state it is in with R. P. Feynman's Q.E.D,
1254 whose apparatus can logically derive the Schrodinger equation have been futile
1255 primarily because the underlying mathematical description of the postulates of
1256 GR are hinged upon that of Riemann and Differential Geometry, which are hinged
1257 upon Lemma, Laws, and Theorems which are proven by the underlying Axioms
1258 of Geometry which have been proven time and time again. The information which
1259 is causing the disjunction of the results calculable from the theoretical framework
1260 that is both theoretical descriptions of "The Universe in its entirety" and the
1261 known inadequate settlements of fields which are inherently opposite in nature,
1262 that is the fields which are dominant in the respectively distant spatial
1263 descriptions.

1264 The Riemann Zeta function is a Scalar Complex valued function which
1265 is defined as the convergence of the Euler-Product and the infinite sum over n of
1266 n as n is multiplied into itself a multiple of s times. The Euler-Product provides
1267 information about the distribution of the Prime Numbers, and so by definition, as
1268 does the Riemann Zeta function. Operating the Taylor Expansion on Z produces
1269 Coefficients to the ∞ th order polynomial which are exponential with respect to a,
1270 number a which when is of value zero produces the Maclaurin Series. It is clear
1271 that because the Prime Numbers can be defined by many interpreters, the Riemann
1272 Zeta Function provides an intricate properties that is inherent in the definition of
1273 simple numbers like 1, 2, 3... because the Prime Numbers are defined with respect
1274 to an Interpreter. Interpreters are people like me who use theories like QED and
1275 GR to explain the Events in the Universe in a precise mathematical fashion, and
1276 so the very definition of the Riemann Zeta function, because it is related to the
1277 Euler-Product is dependent upon the relative definition of the Prime Numbers. It

1278 is from Euler that the relation $e^{i\pi} = -1$, exists, and a proof by him in *The*
 1279 *Introductio* to show, without using the continuum operations of Calculus, so to
 1280 treat the basis of Numbers, in the form which is most correct in the sense that the
 1281 Algebraic operations used to derive the series definitions of the sine and cosine
 1282 functions whose inherent pattern, become related to the exponential through the
 1283 introduction of the Complex exponential. The definition is produced by a limit,
 1284 which is nowadays rudimentary Calculus, where the relationship of the Complex
 1285 exponential to the sinusoidally varying Complex Plane is guaranteed by the affine
 1286 relationship that exists between the Polynomial definitions of the sine and cosine
 1287 which were discovered by Euler's recognition of the small angle approximations
 1288 to that of the exponential versus these two functions..

1289 An exponential function which is raised to a single Real variable
 1290 multiplied into the Imaginary Unit produces a function which is Complex, and not
 1291 Real. It is thus clear that for Relativistic Field Theories which have co-ordinates
 1292 which are defined only to be Real, the solutions to the differential equations, due
 1293 to the inherent nonlinear nature of the Field and Geodesic Equations will be
 1294 Complex. The fact that the solutions come out to be Complex; an example is the
 1295 wave equation of GR in the Weak Field Limit; tells us that we must consider a
 1296 mathematical framework, and because of the intricate connection to the postulates
 1297 of such a theory, intuitive and Philosophical construction of the Events and
 1298 Objects within the Universe, that is Complex Valued to its most general extent, if
 1299 it wishes to be a deterministic description of the trajectories of particles which
 1300 clearly exhibit these qualities. Energy is a relative concept, and so, it depends as
 1301 to which dimension the interpreter is inquiring from as to how the problem will
 1302 be explained. Someone who thinks in Red may think the world that exists is
 1303 different than that of the world of the Blue, but clearly, independent of the
 1304 definition, the world is and always has been the same world, with respect to all
 1305 interpreters and thinkers who have and ever will exist.

1306
 1307 **Definition: Anti-Particles**

1308
 1309 Let us define the Energy of the particle as E_p , velocity of the particle as
 1310 v_p , and V , the potential on the particle.

1311
 1312 $E_p(x', y', z', t') = \frac{m}{2} v_p^2(x', y', z', t') + V(x', y', z', t')$, is a tiny energy that is
 1313 hard to view for us, so viewing it with the scaling wave function, $\psi(x', y', z', t')$, will
 1314 allow for us to see it better,

$$0 = -\psi E_p + \psi \frac{m}{2} v_p^2 + \psi V \quad \text{Eq 95}$$

1315 If we are viewing a particle in free space which has respectively zero velocity
 1316 (with respect to a macroscopic viewer), but we think that the particle has energy,
 1317 then the de Broglie momentum-wavelength relation is logical. With such an
 1318 insertion, the velocity will appear to take the form of a partial derivative on the
 1319 wave function, which will lead to the wave solution for the electric field in free
 1320 space (zooming in to view life as that quantum particle). Generally, the probability
 1321 of finding the particle can be obtained by the complex squaring of the wave
 1322 function [117], after of course, the normalization [118] of the function has
 1323 occurred. Schrödinger found that this wave function obeys the differential
 1324 equation:

$$0 = -i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t'} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x'^2} + V\psi. \quad \text{Eq 96}$$

1325 So that for a quantum velocity, as considered from the De Broglie-Bohm
 1326 Theory, this would produce, as expected, \mathbb{C} velocities, particles with a \mathbb{R} velocity
 1327 and an \mathbb{I} particle. I found, if supposing particles have a Quantum Velocity ; that

1328 this velocity has to be defined over all space, because it is a function of the
1329 curvilinear Quantum Metric [119], quantum space-time [120] on the Quanta-
1330 dimension; to be proportional to the square root of the wave function.

1331 § 5.8) Mathematical Topics Which are Relevant to 9

1332 Just before I begin part one, I mention how to imagine thinking of what
1333 functions of Complex Variables is like; namely, the continuous transport of the
1334 variable $x + iy$, to the new variable $U + iV$, where U and V are functions of the
1335 scalar valued numbers x , and y (As described by Riemann [122]). This shows later
1336 on that when one is thinking of these surfaces; namely, the real and the imaginary,
1337 one must consider in total five dimensions. The full analysis of the function
1338 $f(x + iy) = u + iv$ has f, U, V, x, y all as axes which are perpendicular to one
1339 another. Consider how each of these five variables are with respect to one another:
1340 there would be no function to analyze, had we not first designated a co-ordinate
1341 plane which can be thought of as scaled measuring rods (number line), and how
1342 this number system we thought of changes if we perform a number transformation
1343 on the co-ordinates to arrive at $U + iV$. The inverse transformation [123] will
1344 lead us back to the original co-ordinates $x + iy$, once been applied to the variable
1345 $U + iV$. Transformations of this type are the key to the henceforth sections about
1346 continuity being forced on the transformation operation [124].

1347 In **1.0**), I start by depicting how Complex numbers can be visualized in
1348 component form as a two vector. This conception is interesting because from here,
1349 Special Relativity is summarized very quickly. This is why here, I will talk about
1350 the theory: The idea of Relativity is that because of philosophies like Descartes,
1351 which are fundamentally true, objects can be imagined to be "localized" at a place
1352 in space and time which is described by three perpendicular rulers and a clock.
1353 Clearly motion does not exist without the parameter of time, for without a change
1354 in time, nothing would be happening. The exploitation of these thoughts onto
1355 human beings who think about life with Electromagnetic waves, depict the
1356 bounding of one electromagnetic viewer (thing who thinks) to another, and it is
1357 thus this conception which asks, that if we can understand how life evolves with
1358 respect to ourselves, how can all of us agree on a single fundamental truth,
1359 independent of our prejudices?

1360 We are an object in space which can be described by the parameter time,
1361 and thus can be described by mathematical co-ordinates. These "co-ordinates" can
1362 also be called "dimensions," so in the case of human beings, there are four
1363 dimensions describing the "location" of space and time, where for short, we say
1364 "space-time," and these co-ordinates are constituent of the notion of "forward,
1365 back, left, right, up, down" for space, and "temporal distance," for time and
1366 denoted by (in the case of "flat co-ordinates," (see the definition of a system which
1367 is Cartesian (permanently orthogonal), and thus obeys the Pythagorean identity,
1368 $s^2 = \sum(x_n^2)$), x, y, z , at (for in the case of Relativity, $a = ic = \text{sqrt}(-1)$)*speed
1369 of Electromagnetic Wave propagation* (see Maxwell's Electrodynamics), so that
1370 for a vector describing this space (this is the idea of Minkowski's "World"), the
1371 co-ordinates are taken to be the axes themselves, so that the total dimension of the
1372 vector is four, and so that further, with orthogonal axes, $s^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 +$
1373 $a^2t^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - c^2t^2$, where $\vec{s} = \langle ict, x, y, z \rangle$. Now, if we wish to
1374 think of the event which is described still yet Cartesian axes, but from a
1375 perspective x', y', z', ict' which does not have $x' = x, y' = y, z' = z, t' =$
1376 t , but instead that the primed co-ordinates which understand an event from a
1377 perspective not equal to, but described by Cartesian axes, also obey, the rule that
1378 each observer has a unique perspective, $\vec{s}' = \langle ict', x', y', z' \rangle$; namely that
1379 $s'^2 = x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2 - c^2t'^2$, so that an event is bounded by the maximum speed
1380 of observation; namely, c , the speed of light, which was originally determined by
1381 the uncoupling of Maxwell's Equations Of Electrodynamics, to find that such a

1382 speed is equal to one over the root of the multiplication of the permittivity and
1383 permeability of free space, whose values are present in Coulombs Force Law, and
1384 the Lorentz Force Law. These thoughts are implicative of the speed of the
1385 propagation of light being the same for everyone. This is one of the postulates of
1386 Relativity, and this was confirmed experimentally by the Morely-Michelson
1387 Interferometer Experiment [125]. For a flat space, the Lorentz Transformations,
1388 which have been proven to be both theoretically (first) and experimentally tested
1389 for use to assist society through the gps [126] for truth, are the bounding equations
1390 of any two flat perspectives.

1391 **§ 6 Definitions Used in CGR:**

1392 **Spatial Co-ordinates**

1393 In a 3-D Cartesian system [127] of co-ordinates, there are three spatial
1394 co-ordinates, x, y, z , forward, back, left, right, up, down. Spatial co-ordinates are
1395 defined in CGR with respect to the problem, or question the inquirer wishes to
1396 solve, or ask. The framework of CGR requires that at any given time, each
1397 problem is Unique in the Universe which began with what Humans of Earth
1398 designate as "spatial co-ordinate," and hence in the framework which models
1399 such. It is so that, in CGR, at any given instant in the Universe, it may be true that
1400 the temporal co-ordinates change to spatial co-ordinates, where this will occur at
1401 places of strong space-time curvature, like that of the Event Horizon of a Black
1402 Hole [128]. Spatial co-ordinates are defined as the positive numbers which
1403 compose the Scalar valued Interval with respect to the parameter t .

1404 **Temporal Co-ordinates**

1405 In CGR, time is a unit of measurement, no different than the usage of
1406 rulers for determining a spatial measurement, and is determined by the fact that
1407 relative motion of a system is occurring, like that of the arm of a clock, which
1408 moves with respect the circuitry of the battery, that is fueled by chemical
1409 interactions that are composed of interacting molecules, and hence collections of
1410 Particles that are moving with respect to one another. This is the same
1411 fundamental truth in every system, that in order for inquisition to be understood
1412 by such an apparatus, time must have passed because the inquisition is composed
1413 of logical Human thought, where thought is composed of information, which is in
1414 the form of symbols, characters, sounds, and infinitely other characterizing
1415 properties of the environment that are instances of exhibition of prior knowledge
1416 to form a "thought" which is representative of the collection of knowledge, and
1417 biological capacity in a sense that information becomes defined with a numerical
1418 value. Because then, even information becomes defined numerically. Time is
1419 determined by the relative motion of an object, where this defined with respect to
1420 someone who has the ability to inquire. It is thus that because the inquirer who is
1421 thinking in at least 3-D spatial systems, where change can occur in these systems,
1422 and that by the definition of spatial co-ordinates, time is the negative numbers that
1423 compose the Scalar valued Interval with respect the 4-D observer.

1424 **γ – Vector**

1425 Consider a 3-D Cartesian co-ordinate system with origin $(0, 0, 0)$, where
1426 at (x, y, z) , \exists the surface of a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ Rubik's cube. It is clear that if we solve
1427 each of these cubes solved simultaneously and imagine in this thought
1428 experiment, that every Cube from $(0, 0, 0)$ to (∞, ∞, ∞) is scrambled in a way
1429 that every time one solves this imaginary infinite system of cubes, with a method

1430 that is amended in a predictable manner to generate a method to solve cube
1431 situated at $(3\bar{x}, 3\bar{y}, 3\bar{z})$, which is effectively the spatial location of the origin
1432 of the experiment which is within our 3-D realm of thought. If we require that in
1433 this thought experiment, the only truth which is true is the fact that one cube can
1434 only solve, when all the others can solve, what becomes true necessarily, that
1435 because there exist infinitely many scaled versions of the same object, which
1436 moves in time, that we must consider that our co-ordinates take a completely
1437 different description in in the realm of thought, in the sense that for a solution
1438 method which can produce for the cubes to solve at the same time, even in this
1439 imaginary experiment, it must be well defined, and be able to be described
1440 mathematically by the rules which compose the problem's description. In forcing
1441 true absolutely, at least with additional co-ordinates, logical continuity in the
1442 experiment which has been defined by the 5-D thinker, one who can imagine
1443 solving a Rubik's cube, we find that for the observer who understands that 5-D
1444 thinkers cannot actually fathom the described thought experiment, unless they did
1445 so with the operation of zoom, to respectively consider a system which is
1446 collective of ∞ Rubik's cubes. We must consider dimensions beyond that which
1447 are defined within the problem because the problem asks of a task which cannot
1448 be performed continuously in 3-D. We consider vectors with γ co-ordinate axes,
1449 where γ is defined as the minimum number to force the sought thought experiment
1450 to be true, provided its definition as understood by at least the postulates of CGR.
1451 A γ – Vector is a vector with γ Dimensions.

1452 **Space-time**

1453 Newton's Second Law is mathematically identical to the statement $F -$
1454 $ma = 0$, where this statement effectively is a statement that the existence of the
1455 second derivative of the trajectory, otherwise, the acceleration of a rigid body
1456 implies the existence of a function of the co-ordinates known as a Force. This
1457 existence is because of the fact that for a change in motion to exist, time must
1458 have passed, and so, because of COE which guarantees that the Euler-Lagrange
1459 methodology is applicable to describe the analysis, there are energy functions
1460 which can produce the forces that are required for a change in such a rigid body's
1461 position were time to progress even an instant. The description of energy functions
1462 which describe the set of information for the analysis of the motion of a rigid body
1463 is effectively the description of space-time, after we introduce the postulates of
1464 CGR which begin to view space-time [129] as a network of information which
1465 describes the evolution of a Universe.

1466 **Conservation of Energy**

1467 COE is fundamentally true in the respect that the rate of change of kinetic
1468 energy in time, the energy of an Object [130], Particle [131], or System of Objects
1469 [132] which pertains to the relative motion of a system which has been defined
1470 with respect to other Systems of Objects, Particles etc....

1471 **Geodesic Equations**

1472 Geodesic equations provide a relationship that the respective co-
1473 ordinates will obey inside of a space-time, much like the Classical acceleration is
1474 in accordance with the Force acting upon the body.

1475 **Definition of Zoom Operator**

1476 The notion of zoom is not new as spatial zooming is seen by anyone who
 1477 has used google maps [133] or any video game and temporal zooming [134] by
 1478 people who have watched videos. This can be viewed as an operator and used to
 1479 construct CGR.

1480 The vectors which describe the Interval of a particle on the Quantuadimension,
 1481 Electrodimension, and the Astrodimension respectively are ${}^v_n S_\mu^n, {}^v_n S_\mu^n, {}^v_n S_\mu^n$. These
 1482 vectors describe effectively all information in the Universe. They describe the
 1483 Real and Imaginary happenings of a Universe of information and are designed
 1484 with respect to a 5-D viewer. This viewer has to imagine different dimensions
 1485 which are with respect to the 5-D description on that dimension. To go from one
 1486 dimension to the next, is to zoom, where zoom is this operation. It is a limit
 1487 operation to take a 5-D observer to a new co-ordinate plane which is describing
 1488 the same event but that has been numerically scaled in a manner which has been
 1489 specified by the person performing the operation.

1490
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) = {}^v_n S_\mu^n \quad \text{Eq 97)}$$

1491
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) = {}^v_n S_\mu^n \quad \text{Eq 98)}$$

1492
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) = {}^v_n S_\mu^n \quad \text{Eq 99)}$$

1493
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) = {}^v_n S_\mu^n \quad \text{Eq 100)}$$

1494
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) \neq {}^v_n S_\mu^n \quad \text{Eq 101)}$$

1495 Because of the polynomial representation of such a system of
 1496 information, there exists a polynomial definition of the zoom operation much as
 there does for the logarithm.

1497
$$\text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(t-a)^k \frac{d^k \text{Zoom}({}^v_n S_\mu^n)}{dt^k}}{k!} \quad \text{Eq 102)}$$

Electrodimension (sub micron to radius of universe)

1498 This is the respective plane of 4-D measurement, where electricity is the
 1499 dominating field. A dynamic electric field produces a magnetic field term in
 1500 Maxwell's equations, which was shown mathematically by Maxwell and was
 1501 sought because of Faraday's electromagnetic induction experiment which shows
 1502 the relationship of the happenings of an electric circuit to the magnetic phenomena
 1503 which is inherently due to the relative motion of the electrons that is created a
 1504 circuit when an external voltage force is applied across the wires that are
 1505 composed of copper and are connected to electrical components of various natures
 1506 with respect to the electrons which carry the property spin whose sum of spins
 1507 inside the material which has a mass and hence energy distribution whose sum

1508 converges to the existence of a magnetic field, known as a ferromagnetic core, in
1509 the example of a iron solenoid, inductor. This electricity fluid is visualized
1510 mathematically, in the respect that it obeys these postulates. The E-Field is
1511 effectively a classical limit of a space-time representation of the electromagnetic
1512 phenomena. Once we add the magnetic terms to the equations, where because of
1513 the Liénard–Wiechert Potentials, we understand that the magnetic terms are
1514 actually additional terms of the electric field which are created due to the relative
1515 motion of the objects which spawn the phenomena in question. In such a case, the
1516 terms, at least at the point of measurement, that is, the point with which we
1517 physically assign a value to the variable in the problem, and determine the
1518 numerical output. The magnetic force terms and the electric force terms are
1519 numerically superimposed, and so the space-time description is able to be done
1520 by the fact that the underlying numerical structure we understand in effect, codes
1521 the symbolic theory, and CGR is designed to be able to flow with respect to the
1522 numerical outputs of a given theory that is within the definition of the Universe.
1523 In effect, the Electro-Dimension is the dimension where the numbers are of a
1524 magnitude that we are familiar. With respect, the operation of zoom will have to
1525 take us to be infinitely small to understand the Quanta-Dimension, and infinitely
1526 far to understand the Astro-Dimension. The Electro-Dimension is the where
1527 pressure variations strike one's hearing orifices when a Space ship which uses
1528 momentum conservation techniques through the expense of fuel for propulsion
1529 lifts off because the rocket reaches velocities which are supersonic and which are
1530 hence described by a Mach number. This is because the variations themselves are
1531 respective displacements, and hence measurable actions with a certain set of
1532 numbers which entirely specify the problems electrical phenomena, in the respect
1533 that the objects of relative interest are composed of various different materials, in
1534 the case of a rocket, steel, aluminum, various insulation type materials which are
1535 specifically designed for the respective abuse that a rocket will take when leaving
1536 the atmosphere, and while it is in travel, and so that these materials are composed
1537 of the various Elements of the Periodic Table [133], and that follow the laws of
1538 Quantum Mechanics because the various composing molecules [134] of the
1539 materials [135] that compose the space ship [136] are with respect to the dynamics
1540 of atoms [137], because atoms altogether structure such. It is thus that the laws of
1541 the Particle mechanics [138] are in the negative respect, a zoom of the dynamics
1542 which occur on the Electro-Dimension. In accordance with such an idea,
1543 Astro-dimension is the performing of zoom in the positive sense with respect to
1544 the Electro-Dimension.

1545 **Quanta-Dimension (sub Planck scale: $10^{-\infty}$ to hundreds of thousands of**
1546 **molecular radii)**

1547 It is thus that the laws of the Particle mechanics are in the negative
1548 respect, a zoom of the dynamics which occur on the Electro-Dimension. The
1549 describing functions of the Schrodinger probabilistic analysis [139] determine
1550 with generality, experiments of large quantity, in the sense that there is much data
1551 to come to predictions of the future. The deterministic description [140] simply
1552 tells us how it happened, and this is what CGR offers due to its generalizable
1553 properties. The Quanta-Dimension is the respective numerical realm where the
1554 known particle mechanics as found from the Standard Model [141] is dominant.
1555 A zoom in the positive sense on the co-ordinates which are within the numerical
1556 realm designated as the Quanta-Dimension will transport the problem to terms
1557 understandable on a numerical dimension which is denoted by color towards the

1558 Electro-Dimension. An electron which is in the immediate vicinity of a single
1559 Proton Nuclei [142] with atomic weight of 1 amu. is described with well enough
1560 accuracy by the insertion of the Coulomb Potential for the Potential function
1561 which is present by the time dependent Schrödinger wave equation. This equation
1562 provides one, once coupled with the statistical interpretation of Born [143], a way
1563 to determine the probability distribution of the electron with respect to the proton.

1564 **Astro-Dimension (distances for microgravity between molecules to 10^{∞})**

1565 The Heavenly Bodies [144] lie on numerical realms with respect to the
1566 Electro-Dimension which are of magnitudes which are simply respectively too
1567 large to use in a paper, and so performing the zoom operation in the positive sense
1568 on the Electro-Dimension will produce numerically valued co-ordinates which are
1569 towards the Astro-Dimension. Because there is no distance which bounds either
1570 of these two definitions, it is simply understood that the numbers are respectively
1571 infinitely large, the exact placement of the name, Astro-Dimension, Quanta-
1572 Dimension, or Electro-Dimension for that matter is arbitrary.

1573 **Mass**

1574 Mass is the amount of matter in a system we wish to understand. Special
1575 Relativity guarantees us that mass is equal to energy through the equality
1576 $E=mc^2\gamma$. In now asking what energy is, we have usually arrived to the cyclic
1577 definition that is impossible to define. The discovery of the Higgs Boson [145]
1578 implies the existence of the Higgs field [146]. This field is what "gives" particles
1579 their mass, well, the existence of it. In CGR, this is much the same, but because
1580 we have characterized energy as a color, and thus number, we can characterize
1581 mass in a similar respective manner. The definition of mass is in proportion to this
1582 number. Mass is a number which can be variable in systems. Consider variable
1583 density and Volume of an Object: $dm = \rho dV + d\rho V$. Mass can also be thought
1584 of as sums of N Object's masses. Mass can be the sum of a collection of K systems
1585 which are composed of J Objects.

1586 In the "Perfect Frame" of Reference, The mass of the Universe [147] is
1587 a sum of the respectively moving Systems of masses which include Nebulae,
1588 Galaxies, and considerably, clusters of clusters of Galaxies which orbit clusters
1589 of Galaxies which are composed of Black holes, Solar-systems, etc... which each
1590 are then sums of inner Earth Solar-System type objects of perhaps different
1591 variants like silicon based entities as opposed to carbon based D.N.A replication
1592 processes [148], the sums of the Elements which thus compose such and the sums
1593 of the masses of the atom's respective mass, to which one imagines summing the
1594 masses of the individually respectively interacting subatomic particles, repeating
1595 this process towards infinity.

1596 Clearly mass is a relative conception, because it is the coefficient in the
1597 equations which define the energy functions, which are relative by the definition
1598 that the co-ordinate axes are relative through the definition of the Lorentz
1599 transformation, again, $E = mc^2\gamma$. There is seemingly an equivalence between the
1600 Higgs field mechanism and the energy embedded within the generalized space
1601 time.

1602 **Energy**

1603 A definition of energy for the Electro-Dimension exists though the
1604 existence of the Euler-Lagrange Equations. Energy is with respect to a 4-D
1605 observer, a 5-D surface. This surface is described in § 3. Energy, also is the coding
1606 information for any problem. Energy has an analogous definition for each
1607 dimension and each property of matter.

1608 **The speed of light:**

1609 The speed of light has been experimentally verified to be $c \approx 3E8$ m/s,
1610 and by the Maxwell equations, $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}}$. Due to the second postulate of Relativity,
1611 observers within any given universe are bounded by this rate of information
1612 exchange.

1613 **What is charge?**

1614 Electric charge is a property of matter that causes for two respectively
1615 "charged" particles to feel a force of attraction or repulsion. In CGR, we are able
1616 to define charge and any other new properties of matter not discussed here,
1617 through the definition of energy. Just as mass helps to determine the energy
1618 function which describes the system, charge also shapes the energy of the system.

1619 **What is Gravity?**

1620 Gravity is the force which is dominant on the Astrodimension. On the
1621 Quantadimension, the force terms caused by mass is respectively tiny, but sum of
1622 many trillions of trillions of interacting atoms produce objects which, with respect
1623 to one another experience a force. Gravity is the name of the force that any
1624 respective large bodies will feel. In GR, as in CGR, we replace the idea of "force"
1625 with the conception of "space-time curvature." Intuitively, these concepts are
1626 similar to one another. The idea of space-time, however, is a far more
1627 mathematically precise definition, for it shows explicitly that co-ordinates are
1628 relative to one another.

1629 **What is a photon?**

1630 A photon is the force carrier of the Electromagnetic force. If an electron
1631 absorbs [149] a photon [150], the electron's energy [151] state becomes excited,
1632 where the respective energy of the electron becomes increased. This increase of
1633 energy is discrete, and is in CGR, a \mathbb{I} particle which travels at the speed of light.
1634 The increase of imaginary energy causes for the \mathbb{R} part of the quantum velocity of
1635 the electron to increase. This is reflected by the change of the expected probability
1636 distribution for the particle.

1637 **Electron**

1638 An electron is a discrete point defined by space-time co-ordinates which
1639 has properties which affect the environment.

1640 Imagine the Double Slit Experiment [152] where we fire a single electron
1641 with an Electron Gun [153] at the slits of an experimental setup where suppose
1642 we do not observe anything other than the click on the screen which is produced
1643 when the electron materializes at the screen after its traversing from the gun,
1644 because the screen is connected to a computer monitor which senses the electrical
1645 presence of the electron at a particular point in the screen due to the nearing
1646 electron's acceleration [154] with respect to the screen. The Intensity distribution
1647 [155] which describes after firing many electrons at the screen will be in
1648 proportion to the sinc squared function [156], where this is experimental
1649 verification that electrons themselves obey the probability distribution of the
1650 Schrodinger wave function, where we know because of the work of R. P Feynman
1651 which allows for Quantum Electrodynamics to derive the wave mechanics of
1652 Schrodinger, that the electron has the characteristics of spin [157], which means
1653 it has a permanent in all respects magnetic dipole moment [158], which is shown
1654 by the Stern-Gerlach Experiment [159]. Theoretically the relative motion which
1655 creates this permanent magnetic dipole moment is the quantum velocity which
1656 exists because of the respective de Broglie frequency [160]. The existence of this
1657 wave velocity implies for sake of completion of the thought experiment [161],
1658 that a quantum velocity exists for the electron, this permanent existence is in
1659 accordance with the wave-like numerical nature of Complex functions

1660 **Particles**

1661 Particles are a point within a mathematically defined space which carry
1662 the properties of matter.

1663 **Energy of a Particle**

1664 The Energy of a Particle [162] is with respect to the (Dimensional
1665 location, Space-time Location) that the observer wishes to analyze the energy of
1666 the Particle. The Energy of a Particle is defined as the Kinetic Energy [163] of the
1667 Particle summed to the Potential Energy [164] of the Particle. The Potential
1668 Energy of a Particle is defined as negative the time Integral of the time total-
1669 derivative of the Kinetic Energy of a Particle. The Work done on a Particle in
1670 Classical Mechanics [165] is a quantity which can be determined experimentally
1671 through means of measurement, and theoretically, the work provides a description
1672 of the Kinetic Energy. The Kinetic Energy on the Electro-Dimension for a Particle
1673 in a permanently Cartesian space-time is given by Einstein's mass energy
1674 equivalence, $E = mc^2\gamma$ where after operating Taylor's Theorem on γ , we find that
1675 if $v \ll c$, $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + mc^2$. This is in accordance with the Work-Energy theorem
1676 of James Prescott Joule [166].

1677 **Element**

1678 The elements [167] are composed of Atoms, where Atoms are
1679 constituent of a relatively positively charged atomic nuclei that is composed of
1680 Protons [168] and Neutrons [169] which are composed of Quarks [170], with
1681 respect to the negatively charged electron cloud that surrounds the atoms of
1682 varying sizes. The Elements are described by the Periodic Table and vary in size
1683 from as of right now, the smallest atom, a single proton Hydrogen atom [171],
1684 and the largest being that of Francium [172].

1685 **Molecules**

1686 Molecules [173] are composed of interacting atoms. Molecules are a
1687 structure of atoms [174] which interact primarily because of the respective electric
1688 potentials that exist for a given configuration of Elements. This is essentially
1689 solved for by solving the many body Schrodinger equation [175]. What are the
1690 lagrangian functions for each molecule?

1691 **Energy of a Molecule**

1692 The energy of a Molecule is the sum of the energies of all the considered atoms
1693 which compose the Molecule with respect to the environment that the molecule is
1694 inside, which is with respect to the inquirer of the Energy of the Molecule. An
1695 example is dihydrogen monoxide [176].

1696 **Objects**

1697 Objects are composed of interacting Molecules or Schrodinger dynamics
1698 for groups of molecules [177]. Objects are systems of Molecules. An example is
1699 a golf club. How can we define what an object is specifically?

1700 **Energy of an Object**

1701 Energy of an Object [178] is the sum of the energies of all the Energies
1702 of the Molecules which compose the Object with respect to the environment that
1703 the Object is in with respect to the observer who is inquiring of the energy of the
1704 Object.

1705 **Systems**

1706 Systems [179] are defined as a set of Objects, where systems follow the
1707 same laws with respect to other systems that Objects follow with respect to other
1708 objects, just as within Objects, Particles are with respect to one another. A solar
1709 system [180] is such an example.

1710 **Energy of a System**

1711 The Energy of a System [181] is defined as the sum of the energies of
1712 the Objects which compose the System with respect to the environment that the
1713 System is within with respect to the inquirer of the energy of the System.

1714 **Collection of Systems: Bounded Universes**

1715 COS's are with respect to other COS's in the same respective manner that
1716 the objects within a system are with respect to one another.

1717 **Universe**

1718 The Universe [182] is defined as the set of all COS's.

- 1719 **Energy of the Universe**
- 1720 The Energy of the Universe [183] is defined as the sum of the energies
1721 of all relative systems within the Universe with respect to surrounding Universes
1722 with respect to the inquirer of the energy of the Universe.
- 1723 **Multiverse**
- 1724 Multiverses [184] are Universes which are with respect to one another.
1725 It is s structure of many Universes.
- 1726 **Energy of Multiverse**
- 1727 Energy of the Multiverse the sum of the energies of the respective
1728 Universes with respect to the inquirer of the energy of the Multiverse.
- 1729 **Antiparticles**
- 1730 Antiparticles [185] are characterized as the Imaginary components with
1731 respect to Real components of Particles.
- 1732 **AntiElements**
- 1733 AntiElements [186] are the Elements described by the Imaginary
1734 components to the description of the Real matter which describes the respective
1735 Element.
- 1736 **Antiphotons [187]**
- 1737 **AntiMolecule**
- 1738 AntiMolecules [188] are the Molecules described by the Imaginary
1739 components to the description of the Real matter which describes the respective
1740 Molecules.
- 1741 **AntiObjects**
- 1742 AntiObjectsare the Objects described by the Imaginary components to
1743 the description of the Real matter which describes the respective Object.
- 1744 **AntiSystems**
- 1745 AntiSystems are the Systems described by the Imaginary components to
1746 the description of the Real matter which describes the respective System.
- 1747 **AntiUniverse**

1748 AntiUniverses [189] are the Universes described by the Imaginary
1749 components to the description of the Real matter which describes the respective
1750 Universe.

1751 **AntiMultiverse**

1752 AntiMultiverse are the Multiverses described by the Imaginary components to the
1753 description of the Real matter which describes the respective Multiverse.

1754 **Wave-Particle Duality**

1755 Particles exhibit wavelike and particle like properites [190].

1756 The Schrödinger description provides us with the fact that \exists a wave-like
1757 feature of matter at the Planck Length of measurement, and so the mathematical
1758 description, which makes sure that the definitions of the electron maintain the
1759 same throughout the problem, that the point-like Cartesian description of the
1760 problem is still also applicable. CGR rectifies this issue with the addition of
1761 AntiParticles, which are required by Symmetry, as being the mathematically
1762 defined Imaginary components of the Particles. This definition inherently creates
1763 the definition of AntiObjects, AntiSystems, etc... The quality which Complex
1764 Numbers have is swirly. It is the inverse nature of the root of negative one, which
1765 makes the necessity of Analyticity, and it is Analyticity which is required for
1766 continuity. The quantum velocity of Particles have a Real Part which is the
1767 electron in the case of The Slit Experiment and an Imaginary Part which is the
1768 AntiParticle. This explains the permanently relative wave-like features of matter.

1769 **Photon**

1770 Consider an electron in free space. If we trap the electron in a well and
1771 subject it to Electromagnetic radiation of whose intensity, frequency, amplitude,
1772 and wavelength are properties we determine by the devices we have designed for
1773 this experimentation, we know given the various slightly different initial
1774 conditions that can cause the experiment to vary slightly. We know that the
1775 Electromagnetic Radiation is induced by the relative oscillatory acceleration of
1776 the electron current inside of the device which is being used to create the radiation
1777 in the first place, so the EM radiation which will undoubtedly change the -
1778 respective to free space- measurements will by some maximum or minimum
1779 measurement which is produced by the maximum and minimum initial conditions
1780 of the device which is emitting the radiation. This is where experimental
1781 uncertainty comes in. The initial conditions are effectively random always
1782 because we as humans cannot feasibly map and control every aspect of the energy
1783 which exists throughout the infinitude of space. It is however, that we can come
1784 to consistent calculable results which serve as the backbone of our understanding.
1785 The absorption of a Photon for electron in free space is effectively the absorption
1786 of a discrete amount of energy from the EM wave the particle was subjected to.
1787 We are analyzing a Particle with a collection of particles. This only adds to the
1788 uncertainty of measurement in the respect that the space is filled with photons,
1789 when we subject the electron to radiation in the lab, and so there exists a
1790 measurable probability that the electron will absorb a photon, under a certain
1791 parameterization. There also exists a measurable probability of the position and

1792 energy of the electron. Time passes in these experiments, and so, the test of my
1793 theory would be to track in time, quantum experiments, but yielding individual
1794 instances of the data. Photons are bundles of Energy, which can be seen as an
1795 addition to the energy of the electron, the Particle whose measurements are of
1796 interest. This addition is part Imaginary and part Real, and so if we define the
1797 electron, even without its positron pair, we will see changes in the electron's
1798 energy which remain wave-like. This wave property is due to the fact that the
1799 solution to Maxwell's wave equation in free space is Complex, and which
1800 produces sinusoidally varying solutions.

1801 **Declarations**

1802 DH is the sole contributor of this project; there are no affiliations associated with
1803 this project.

1804 No external funding was used in this project.

1805 Availability of data and materials is not applicable.

1806

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